

EXPERIENCES TOWARD MODULAR LEARNING OF STUDENTS IN THE FRUSTRATION READING LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the challenges faced by students with low reading abilities in a modular learning environment. By interviewing students and parents, the research explored their experiences and perspectives. The findings highlighted the difficulties students had with complex texts and vocabulary, underlining the need for tailored support and differentiated instruction. The study emphasizes the importance of early intervention and scaffolded learning to improve reading proficiency and promote overall academic success. This research contributes to the field of education by advocating for targeted strategies to address the specific needs of struggling readers within modular learning.

Keywords: *Frustration Reading Levels, Modular Learning, Qualitative Research, Educational Interventions.*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a fundamental skill crucial for learning and engaging with various academic subjects. Effective reading allows students to access information, gain insights, and develop critical thinking skills. It forms the foundation for learning new information, expressing ideas, and participating in education.

This study is grounded as revealed in the article by Servallos (2023) published in The Philippine Star, the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) disclosed a substantial educational disparity of five to six years for students in the Philippines, as documented by the Department of Education (DepEd). The mean reading scores for countries participating in the PISA on December 7, 2023, were 476. In contrast,

the Philippines obtained a notably lower score of 347 in reading proficiency. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) elucidates that every 20-point deviation from the average score symbolizes a year's worth of learning pace for 15-year-old students in PISA-participating nations. Regrettably, the Philippines ranked among the lowest 10 out of 81 countries in reading comprehension during the 2022 PISA assessment. Despite a marginal enhancement in rankings, the overall academic performance exhibited minimal advancement. Notably, from 2018 to 2022, the Philippines witnessed a 6.9 percent increase in reading proficiency.

Furthermore, the study recognizes the significance of understanding children's current reading behavior is an area of interest and concern in education (Smith, 2019). Children in today's technologically advanced society are increasingly exposed to a variety of media and entertainment options competing for their attention (Johnson et al., 2020). This shift in behavior has raised questions about the impact of technology on reading habits and literacy skills (Brown & Jones, 2018). Comprehending children's current reading behavior is important for many reasons. For starters, it makes it easier to identify and address potential challenges or obstacles to their reading engagement (Clark, 2017). By identifying these barriers, educators and parents can develop targeted strategies to foster a love of reading and improve reading skills (Davis et al., 2021).

Contributing to the existing body of knowledge on children's reading behavior, this study aims to influence educational strategies and interventions that promote lifelong reading enjoyment and strong literacy abilities (Smith et al., 2022). By understanding how children behave when it comes to reading, learning strategies can be improved and modified to meet their needs and interests in a constantly evolving digital environment (Johnson & Brown, 2021).

Moreover, this study specifically focuses on exploring the experiences of students with frustrated reading levels within the context of modular learning. The goal is to comprehend the factors contributing to their reading difficulties and design personalized interventions to assist struggling readers (Çelik & Uzunboylu, 2020). Addressing these challenges, the study aims to mitigate the prevailing reading proficiency crisis and facilitate the academic advancement of students in one of the schools located within the Second District of Samar (Marohombsar, 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic led to global school closures, making parents into educators. The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines adopted flexible learning modalities, including online and modular learning, developed a Learning Continuity Plan, provided resources, trained teachers, and issued health guidelines. The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) ensured uninterrupted learning through distance modalities, with school administrators selecting the most suitable methods for their contexts (Dargo & Dimas, 2021).

DepEd implemented Modular Learning as an Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM), using self-learning modules (SLMs) focused on essential competencies. Teachers distributed these modules and assessment tools weekly, monitored progress through

home visits, and provided support via distance communication. While practical, Modular Learning posed challenges for struggling readers, requiring them to work independently. Recamara (2018) observed that teachers used reading assessments for documentation without interventions due to time constraints.

In the school year 2020-2021, schools in the Second District of Samar implemented Modular Learning. By the end of the 2021-2022 school year, some schools had limited face-to-face classes, but the modular approach remained dominant. The lack of face-to-face interaction made it difficult to support struggling readers. Over the years, the number of non-readers declined, but the number of students at various reading levels fluctuated. The 2021-2022 school year had the highest number of independent readers, but those struggling with reading comprehension increased, making up 28.07% of total enrollment. These readers were mainly from an upland school where parents, mostly farmers with limited education, struggled with English literacy and technology access.

The data revealed concerning reading performance among students using Modular Learning. Many students struggled to understand their modules, highlighting the need for strategies to improve reading skills. Assessing students' experiences with Modular Learning is crucial to gauge its effectiveness and address the needs of struggling readers (Çelik & Uzunboylu, 2020).

The researcher explored the experiences of students with frustrated reading levels to identify factors contributing to their difficulties and tailor strategies accordingly. Understanding learner engagement and motivation in reading activities within Modular Learning helps design personalized interventions, allowing educators to support struggling readers and enhance overall reading development.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Reading is one of the most extensively researched concepts in contemporary times. The complexity of the topic and multiplicity of studies in reading led the researcher to utilize relevant theories that provide a foundation for the research.

This study was anchored on three fundamental theories, Schema Theory, as proposed by Lyons and Keene (2023), Simple View of Reading (SVRT), introduced by Adams (2019), and the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), a concept developed by Lev Vygotsky.

Schema Theory, as explicated by Lyons and Keene (2023), posits that readers utilize pre-existing knowledge structures, known as schemas, to comprehend text. These schemas function as cognitive frameworks that facilitate the organization and interpretation of new information, especially when encountering unfamiliar content. By activating relevant schemas, readers can connect new information with prior knowledge, bridge knowledge gaps, and ultimately derive meaning from the text.

Students who struggle with reading comprehension, particularly at the frustration level, may have underdeveloped or inadequate schemas in certain subject areas. This can impede their ability to connect with the material presented in the modules. Schema Theory aids this study in understanding student engagement within a modular learning format. If the modules lack sufficient context or connections to existing knowledge, students may struggle to activate relevant schemas, leading to disengagement and difficulty in understanding the material. By comprehending how schemas influence comprehension, educators can examine how the design of the modules affects student experiences.

This theoretical framework provides a basis for analyzing student experiences in modular learning. Utilizing Schema Theory allows an exploration into how comprehension may be impacted for students with reading difficulties due to insufficient background knowledge or inadequately designed modular materials. Understanding the role of schemas can inform the development of instructional strategies that target schema development. This could involve activities that build background knowledge prior to engaging with the modules or the use of graphic organizers to help students visualize connections between existing and new information. Addressing schema gaps and promoting schema activation can potentially enhance learning outcomes for students struggling with reading within a modular learning environment.

The Simple View of Reading Theory (SVRT), proposed by Adams (2019), emphasizes the interplay between decoding and language comprehension in achieving reading comprehension. Decoding refers to the ability to recognize words accurately and fluently, akin to efficiently translating visual symbols into sounds to form words. Strong decoding skills allow readers to recognize familiar words effortlessly, freeing cognitive resources to focus on deeper textual meaning.

Language comprehension, the broader component of SVRT, encompasses a range of skills enabling readers to grasp the meaning of written communication. A robust vocabulary allows readers to understand individual words readily. Grammar knowledge, understanding sentence structure, helps in identifying relationships between words and clauses, leading to clearer comprehension. Background knowledge is crucial as it enables readers to make connections with the text, fill in gaps, and derive a deeper understanding. Additionally, inference skills allow readers to draw conclusions not explicitly stated, using context, prior knowledge, and authorial clues.

SVRT underscores the importance of both decoding and language comprehension for successful reading. It provides a framework for understanding the reading process and the factors contributing to success, thereby equipping educators with tools to foster confident and effective readers. By incorporating SVRT, this study can gain a deeper understanding of the challenges faced by students with frustration-level reading within a modular learning environment.

The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), proposed by Lev Vygotsky, highlights the difference between what a learner can achieve independently and what they can

achieve with guidance and encouragement. Within the ZPD, learners can perform tasks with adequate assistance. Vygotsky suggested that educators should support the learning process through knowledgeable guides and social interactions, enabling learners to practice and develop their skills. Scaffolding activities that support learners through the ZPD can facilitate task completion when learners collaborate with capable peers, teachers, or adults. Conversely, the absence or inadequacy of such support can hinder growth and independent performance.

These theories elucidate the various components involved in the reading process. Integrating these theories into the current study aims to improve learning outcomes for students at the frustration reading level. Insights gained from these theories can help identify potential barriers to learning and inform strategies to overcome them, ultimately enhancing students' reading skills and overall literacy growth.

Scope and Limitations

The study involved interviewing the parents of the students as part of a triangulation method to strengthen the findings and enhance the credibility of the study. By including the perspectives of parents, the research aimed to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the students' experiences towards Modular Learning in the frustration reading level.

However, it is important to acknowledge that the research had certain limitations. The study's primary focus was on children in Grades 3-5 at a single school in the Second District of Samar, which might have limited the findings' applicability to other grade levels or schools. The study did not encompass the perspectives of teachers or explore other factors that may influence students' experiences with Modular Learning. Additionally, the study relied on self-reported data from the students' respective class advisers, which may have some inherent limitations such as potential bias or subjectivity. The use of a purposive sampling method also introduced a potential limitation in terms of the representativeness of the sample. Lastly, it is important to note that the study was conducted during the school year 2022-2023, and the findings may be specific to that period.

Despite these limitations, the research aimed to provide valuable insights into the experiences of students in the frustration reading level towards Modular Learning, and the inclusion of parent perspectives through triangulation added depth and richness to the study's findings.

Research Questions

1. What are the experiences of students identified to be in the frustration reading level toward modular learning?
2. How does the profile of student-respondents (age, birth order, parents' occupation, and parents' highest educational attainment) relate to their experiences toward modular learning?

3. How do students at the frustration reading level perceive the challenges and benefits of modular learning, and how do these perceptions align with parental observations?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research approach utilizing a descriptive phenomenological research design. Descriptive phenomenology was chosen as the methodological framework for its ability to delve deeply into the lived experiences and perceptions of participants concerning frustration reading levels within the context of modular learning (Dangal & Joshie, 2020). Through this descriptive phenomenological lens, the research explored the experiences of students grappling with frustration reading levels within the modular learning setting, aiming to gain a comprehensive understanding of their interpretations, challenges, and motivations. This method facilitated a thorough investigation of their subjective experiences, emphasizing the significance of context in shaping their educational journey.

In-depth interviews were conducted using a semi-structured interview guide, providing an opportunity for the participants to share their personal stories, thoughts, and emotions related to their reading difficulties. To triangulate the data and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the students' experiences, the study included interviews with parents. The inclusion of parent perspectives allowed for a broader view of the challenges faced by students with frustration reading levels in the modular learning context. These interviews with parents provided complementary insights and served as a means to validate and corroborate the students' narratives. The data collected from these interviews were analyzed alongside the student interviews to capture a more holistic understanding of the phenomenon.

The collected data were analyzed using Colaizzi's method of thematic analysis. Colaizzi's method was employed to systematically extract, organize, and describe the key themes and patterns that emerged from the participants' narratives. This rigorous method involves several steps: reading all participant descriptions to acquire a sense of the whole, extracting significant statements, formulating meanings, organizing these meanings into themes, and integrating the findings into an exhaustive description of the phenomenon. This process not only ensured the thoroughness of the analysis but also preserved the richness of the participants' experiences.

By incorporating the perspectives of both students and parents, and utilizing Colaizzi's method for data analysis, the study aimed to provide a well-rounded and comprehensive exploration of the experiences and challenges faced by students with frustration reading levels in the context of modular learning. This research design enabled a nuanced exploration of the phenomenon, providing valuable insights and contributing significantly to the existing body of knowledge in this field.

Research Environment

The research locale for this study was one of the upland schools in the 2nd District of Samar, Philippines. This elementary school adopted Modular Learning as its instructional approach and catered to students from Kindergarten to Grade 6. The school was chosen as the research site due to its distinctive characteristics and context within the district. Specifically, the study aimed to delve into the experiences of students with frustration reading levels at this school, offering insights into the challenges and factors influencing reading difficulties in this educational setting.

Participants of the Study

Qualitative research often employs purposeful sampling based on theoretical principles. In this study, participants were selected using purposive sampling, specifically focusing on students at the frustration reading level. The researcher determined students' frustration reading level through reading assessments conducted by their teachers or class advisers.

Students falling under the frustration level in reading assessments were purposively selected as study participants. This criterion formed the primary basis for participant identification, aiming to gather rich insights into their experiences and attitudes toward Modular Learning. Sample size was determined by data saturation, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the phenomenon within the school's context.

Research Instrument

This study primarily involved the use of a semi-structured interview guide for participants in the frustration reading level. Part of the instrument was to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants, which included their age, birth order, parent's occupation, and parents' highest educational attainment. The interview guide was developed based on the research questions and objectives of the study, with open-ended questions designed to explore the experiences with frustration reading levels toward Modular Learning. The interview guide was flexible, allowing for probing and follow-up questions to delve deeper into specific areas of interest.

To incorporate the triangulation method involving the participants' parents, an additional data collection method was implemented in the form of semi-structured interviews. These interviews were conducted separately with the parents or guardians of the participants to gather their lived experiences and concerns regarding their child's reading performance in the context of modular learning. The interview questions focused on understanding the parents' perspectives on their child's reading difficulties, their observations of their child's progress, and their thoughts on the effectiveness of the modular learning approach.

Validation of Research Instrument

The data gathering instrument in this study underwent content validity assessments. This ensured that the instrument effectively captured the necessary information and was considered appropriate and relevant by experts in the field. Content validity was ensured by reviewing the interview questions by the experts in qualitative research, by the language specialists, and by the Master Teachers in the elementary level.

The interview guide, along with a brief explanation of the study's purpose and the role of their feedback, was shared with the panel members either electronically or in a physical format. They were asked to review the interview guide and provide their feedback on its clarity, relevance, and comprehensibility. The experts were encouraged to suggest any necessary revisions or improvements to the interview guide. The researcher considered the comments and suggestions provided by the experts and used them as a basis for revising the interview guide. Modifications involved rewording questions, clarifying prompts, or adding additional questions to address any areas of concern or ambiguity.

When substantial modifications were made to the interview guide, a second review with the panel members was conducted to confirm and validate the changes. The iterative process of collecting feedback, analyzing it, and refining the interview guide continued until a consensus was reached among the panel members and the researcher on the final version of the interview guide. The input from the panel of experts served as a valuable resource in enhancing the quality and appropriateness of the interview guide for exploring the experiences of students in the frustration reading level within the context of modular learning.

Data Collection Procedure

The researcher secured a letter of approval from the School's Division Superintendent to facilitate the conduct of in-depth interviews with the participants and their parents.

The interviews were semi-structured, guided by interview protocols that explored the participants' experiences related to modular learning and reading performance. The interviews were audio-recorded to ensure accurate data capture, and field notes were taken during and after the interviews to document non-verbal cues and contextual information. The interviews were conducted in a comfortable and private setting, allowing participants to freely express their thoughts and experiences. The data-gathering process prioritized building rapport with the participants and creating a safe and supportive environment for open dialogue.

The collected data were analyzed using Colaizzi's method of descriptive data analysis to explore the experiences of students with frustration reading levels in the context of Modular Learning. Colaizzi's method was used to uncover the underlying

meanings and themes within participants' experiences. The cluster of themes or themes generated underwent validation by experts.

Data Analysis Procedure

This study, being qualitative in nature, did not require statistical data treatment. Instead, Colaizzi's method of descriptive data analysis was utilized to delve into students' experiences with frustration reading levels in Modular Learning. This approach aimed to unveil underlying meanings and themes within participants' encounters. It entailed a systematic process of organizing, analyzing, and interpreting data to yield descriptive and insightful findings. By employing Colaizzi's method, rich insights into the phenomenon under investigation were garnered, shedding light on the essence of participants' experiences (Praveena & Sasikumar, 2021).

In employing Colaizzi's method, a systematic procedure was followed to explore and grasp the nuanced experiences of students dealing with frustration reading levels within modular learning. The researcher immersed herself in the data, thoroughly reviewing participant accounts to gain a comprehensive understanding. Relevant statements regarding modular learning at the frustration reading level were identified, and their meanings were noted, ensuring fidelity to participants' experiences. These meanings were then grouped into common themes, capturing the essence of the phenomenon. From these themes, a detailed description of students' experiences was crafted, aiming to encapsulate their richness and complexity. This comprehensive description was then condensed into a succinct statement, representing the essential aspects of the phenomenon.

In addition to feedback from participants, triangulation with parents' perspectives was employed to validate the findings and potentially refine earlier analysis steps. This involved cross-referencing the insights gathered from students' experiences with modular learning at the frustration reading level against the viewpoints and observations provided by their parents. Through this triangulation method, the study aimed to enhance the credibility of the findings by corroborating them with multiple sources of data, ultimately contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of the investigated phenomenon.

Figure 1. Procedures of Colaizzi's phenomenological descriptive method (Colaizzi, 1978)

Research Reflexivity

The researcher, who also served as the interviewer, took deliberate steps to maintain impartiality throughout the interview process. By avoiding leading questions that could potentially influence participants' responses, the researcher ensured the integrity of the data collected. Moreover, the interviews were conducted in a manner that minimized the researcher's own biases or preconceived notions, further enhancing the validity of the findings. This dedication to confirmability not only spoke to the researcher's commitment as a School Head but also underscored the overarching goal of providing students with the essential skills for effective reading comprehension. Ultimately, this approach guided evidence-based interventions aimed at nurturing students' academic growth and fostering their overall success.

Ethical Considerations

This study followed the ethical standard for the protection and safety of the respondents. The proposal for this research was submitted to the Institutional Research

Ethics Review Committee (IRERC) of Samar State University, where it was reviewed and approved.

Throughout the research process, the researcher ensured voluntary participation by providing clear and comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks to the participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and their anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained throughout data collection, analysis, and reporting. Any sensitive information shared by the participants was handled with utmost discretion and used solely for research purposes. Moreover, participants were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without facing any consequences. The researcher also took measures to minimize any potential harm or discomfort to the participants and remained vigilant for any signs of distress, offering appropriate support and referral services when necessary. Overall, ethical considerations were paramount throughout every phase of the research, ensuring the integrity and trustworthiness of the study's outcomes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Participants

The study includes a diverse group of participants, aged between 9 to 12 years old, who are currently at the frustration reading level and are engaging in modular learning. The average age of the participants is approximately 10.62 years. Their birth orders range from 1st to 9th, with the majority being the 2nd child in their families. It is evident that these learners come from families primarily engaged in farming, as all their parents are farmers. The parents' education levels vary, with some having completed high school, others reaching the elementary level, and a few having no formal schooling at all. Despite the range of educational backgrounds, most parents have at least completed elementary or high school education.

This data provides valuable contextual information about the participants' backgrounds and family situations. The prevalence of farming as the main occupation among parents suggests that these learner - participants may come from rural or agricultural communities. Furthermore, the varying education levels of the parents indicate different levels of exposure to formal education within the participants' households.

Considering these demographics will be essential when interpreting the lived experiences of these learner-participants in the frustration reading level and their engagement in modular learning. The information sheds light on potential socio-economic factors and familial support systems that may influence the learner-participant's experiences and perspectives towards education. It also highlights the need to consider individual differences and backgrounds when analyzing the impact of modular learning on their learning journey. By understanding these demographic characteristics, the

research can better contextualize and interpret the participants' experiences, leading to a more comprehensive and insightful study.

Lived experiences of learners – participants with frustrated reading level toward modular learning

As a result of the exploration of the lived experiences of learners - participants in the frustration reading level within the context of modular learning, three (4) distinct themes emerged. Each of the major themes has its corresponding sub-themes that explain the phenomenon.

Summary of Themes and Sub-themes

THEMES	SUB-THEMES
Challenges Encountered in Modular Learning	Learning Difficulty Due to Overwhelming Students Workload
	Limited Teacher's Guidance and Parental Support
	Economic Challenges and Priorities of Parents
	Lack of Access to Learning Technology
Coping Strategies	Seeking Assistance for Learning
	Time Management and Pro-Active Learning Strategy
	Resort to the copying of Provided Answers in the Module
Students' Challenges in Reading Development	Reading Skills Deficiency
	Difficulty with Academic Reading Materials
	Limited Parental Educational Background and Skills
	Emotional Frustration in Modular Learning
Stakeholders Collaboration for Child's Learning	Home-based Support and Reinforcement
	Peer and Community Support
	Active Teacher Involvement

THEME 1: CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED IN MODULAR LEARNING

Modular learning presents learners with a unique set of challenges that can impede their educational progress and overall well-being. These challenges arise from various factors inherent in the modular learning environment and significantly impact learners' experiences and outcomes. These challenges are explained into three (4) Sub-themes: ***Learning Difficulty due to Overwhelming Students Workload, Limited Teacher's Guidance and Parental Support, Economic Challenges and Priorities of Parents, and Lack of Access to Learning Technology.***

Sub-theme 1.1: Learning Difficulty Due to Overwhelming Students Workload

In modular learning, student-participants grapple with a heavy workload. They are tasked with managing multiple assignments on their own, often within tight deadlines. This can lead to stress, anxiety, and fatigue, making it hard to focus, absorb information,

and perform academically. Additionally, struggling to read the materials compounds these challenges.

Statements that explain this sub-theme are as follows:

[1] "...Nahihirapan po, maraming assignment. Damo na liwat it imu aansweran." Nalilisang na ako ma'am. Diri ako sure han answer ma'am." [I'm having a hard time, there are so many assignments, too many to answer." "I'm already struggling, ma'am. I'm not sure about the answer, ma'am.]" [Participant 8, Lines 488, 494, 498].

[2] "...Ma'am kay mahubya pag-answer, kadadamu an answeran, nalilipong na ak. [Ma'am, because it's hard to answer, there are so many things to answer, I'm starting to struggle.]" [Participant 7, Lines 413-414].

[3] "...May module na ngani Ma'am, mayakan na liwat ako na haggii magbabasa na naman po." Damo tak susuraton. Maguol. [There's already a module, ma'am, but I feel burdened because there's a lot of reading again. There's a lot to discuss. It's distressing.]" [Participant 4, Line 278-279, 281].

The first sub-theme examines the struggles students face in managing their studies, understanding materials, and maintaining academic performance amidst a heavy workload. The statements from student participants highlight the overwhelming nature of the workload, leading to stress, anxiety, and difficulties in focusing and comprehending information. The statements from parents further support these challenges and emphasize the significant burden that modular learning places on students.

[1] "... Kinukurian talaga hiya ma'am salit siguro danay ginpapabay-an nala adto niya an iya module. Nabulig man iya ma'am kun nabisita, ano pa adto an tawag? [He really struggles ma'am, so sometimes he just ignores his module. His teacher helps when she visits.]" [Parent 3 Lines 416-417].

[2] "... Hadto nga modular ma'am bagan masamok manla kami pirmi, bagan hi ako nalilisang gudman pirmi kun may mga answer na ngatanan kay diri man gud hiya nakakabsa pa hin tuhay salit napili la hin aranseran intawon. [During modular learning, ma'am, it was always chaotic for us, I would often get very confused when everything had to have answers because he really couldn't read properly yet, so he would just guess the answers out of pity.]" [Parent 3, Line 404-406].

[3] "... Dahil hindi ako marunong magbasa, nahihirapan akong magbigay ng diretsong gabay sa aking anak sa panahon ng pagsasanay sa pagbasa. Ito ang hadlang sa akin na lubos na suportahan ang kanilang proseso ng pag-aaral. [Because I do not know how to read, I find it difficult to give direct guidance to my child during reading practice. This hinders me from fully supporting their learning process.]" [Parent 5, Line 946-948].

[4] “...Ang pagbasa ng mga mas malalim at mas kumplikadong mga babasahin ay isang hamon para sa aking anak. Ang pag-unawa sa mga malalalalim na salita, mahirap na mga salita, at mga komplikadong pangungusap ay nagdudulot ng pagkabigo sa pag-unawa. [Reading deeper and more complex texts is a challenge for my child. Understanding deep words, difficult words, and complex sentences causes comprehension failure.]” [Parent 4, Line 623-626].

These statements illustrate the multifaceted challenges students face in modular learning, particularly due to the overwhelming workload and lack of sufficient support at home.

The triangulation of responses from both students and parents highlights several key factors that hinder the development of reading skills. Each of these factors has a substantial impact on students' ability to improve their reading proficiency.

Students often experience a sense of overwhelm when faced with educational modules. This overwhelm can stem from the volume of work, the complexity of the tasks, or the pressure to perform well. As a result, their ability to focus on and complete reading assignments is compromised, leading to a decline in reading skills development (Brown, 2020). Overwhelming can cause cognitive overload, where students are unable to process information effectively, thereby reducing comprehension and retention.

Limited time and resources are significant barriers to effective learning. Students who do not have adequate time to dedicate to reading practice or lack access to necessary resources, such as books or digital reading tools, are at a disadvantage. This lack of support hinders their ability to engage in consistent and meaningful reading practice, which is essential for skill improvement (Smith & White, 2019). Time constraints can be due to extracurricular activities, household responsibilities, or part-time jobs, while resource scarcity might stem from socio-economic challenges.

Sub-theme 1.2: Limited Teacher's Guidance and Parental Support

In modular learning, students often face a lack of adequate guidance from teachers and support from parents due to competing household responsibilities, which compounds the challenges they encounter.

[1] “...Siguro Ma’am nakakabulig, dri la ako sure kon tama an akon mga answer han module. Makuri la gud man kay wray man hi teacher pagtutdo ha ak. [Maybe, ma’am, it would help, I’m not really sure if my answers in the module are correct. It’s difficult because there’s no teacher teaching me.]”, “...Makuri kay wray nagtututdo po ha akon, hi Ma’ama ngan Papa nagtratrabaho man, taz hi Teacher kay wray man, dri ako nakakapakiana po. [It’s difficult because there’s no one teaching me, Ma’ama and Papa are working, and the teacher is not there, so I don’t have

anyone to ask.]” , “Makuri po Ma’am an Modular kay wray teacher nagtutudo akon. Nahadlok ak kay bangin ak Zero, wrong akon answer kay talapang la. [Modular learning is difficult because there’s no teacher teaching me. I’m afraid I might get a zero, my answers might be wrong because it’s confusing.]” [Participant 1 Lines 69-70, Participant 8 Lines 534-535, Participant 13 Lines 521-522].

This sub-theme highlights two critical factors hindering a child's reading proficiency: limited teacher guidance and a lack of parental support. Students express their need for guidance from teachers and parents, while parents acknowledge their limited knowledge and resources to provide effective support. The triangulation of responses from both students and parent’s sheds light on the multifaceted challenges that hinder students' learning progress in modular learning.

[1] “...Kinukurian talaga hiya ma’am salit siguro danay ginpapabay-an nala adto niya an iya module. Nabulig man iya ma’am kun nabisita, ano pa adto an tawag? [He really struggles, ma'am, so sometimes he just ignores his module. His teacher helps when she visits.]” [Parent 3, Lines 416-417].

[2] “...Pamati ko ma’am diri man nagkukulang it iya maestra bisan man kun pirmi nal busy. Makuri la talaga tutduan it akon anak kay dinhi ha balay diri ko man pirmi nabubuligan. Danay suguon ko ito nga mamamiling hin makakabulig pag-anser. [I understand, ma’am, that his teacher is lacking even if she’s always busy. It’s really difficult to teach my child because I’m not always available at home. I hope to receive guidance on who can help with the answers.] [Parent 3, Lines 506-508].

[3] “... Dahil hindi ako marunong magbasa, nahihirapan akong magbigay ng diretsong gabay sa aking anak sa panahon ng pagsasanay sa pagbasa. Ito ang hadlang sa akin na lubos na suportahan ang kanilang proseso ng pag-aaral. [Because I do not know how to read, I find it difficult to give direct guidance to my child during reading practice. This hinders me from fully supporting their learning process.]” [Participant 3 Lines 199 and 210].

[4] “... Inaamin ko inuuna naming ang kung may makakain ba kami ngayon kaysa sa pagtuturo sa mga nak ko, pero kung pagturo, konti lang alam ko ma’am. Mahirap talaga kami. [I admit that we prioritize whether we have food to eat today over teaching my children, but when it comes to teaching, I know very little, ma'am. We really struggle.]” [Participant 3 Lines 199 and 210].

[5] “... Diri ako maaram hit iba ma’am, guti la. Diri man liwat ako maaram kun paano ko itututdo it module. Naaro nla ak bulig iya mga kapaturan.” [I don't know about it either, ma'am, it's true. I also don't know

*how to teach the module. Sometimes I ask for help from their elders.]”
[Participant 3 Lines 199 and 210].*

The passage argues that both limited teacher guidance and a lack of parental support can significantly hinder students' reading development (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020; Jeynes, 2021). Teachers who are stretched thin due to large classes or lack of training may not be able to provide the individualized instruction and support students need to grasp reading strategies. Similarly, parents facing limitations like low literacy skills or busy schedules may struggle to reinforce learning at home, creating a gap that demotivates students and hinders their reading progress.

Reliance on external help, such as tutors or supplemental educational programs, can be a double-edged sword. While these resources can provide valuable assistance, an over-reliance on them may indicate that the primary educational support from teachers and parents is insufficient. This reliance can create a dependency that undermines students' confidence in their ability to tackle reading challenges independently. Additionally, not all students have equal access to external help due to financial or logistical constraints, leading to disparities in reading skill development. External help should ideally complement, rather than replace, the foundational support provided by teachers and parents (Muller & Schiller, 2023).

Sub-theme 1.3: Economic Challenges and Priorities of Parents

Economic challenges and priorities refer to the financial constraints and competing demands that parents face, which may hinder their ability to support their children's reading development. Struggles with poverty impact parents' ability to focus on their children's education. Additionally, economic pressures may force parents to prioritize other essential needs over investing time and resources into their children's education, including reading support.

Statements that explain this sub-theme are as follows:

[1] "...Inaamin ko inuuna naming ang kung may makakain ba kami ngayon kaysa sa pagtuturo sa mga nak ko, pero kung pagturo, konti lang alam ko ma'am. Mahirap talaga kami. [I admit that we prioritize whether we have food to eat today over teaching my children, but when it comes to teaching, I know very little, ma'am. We really struggle.]" , "...Siguro ito nga kulang ako hin oras ngan diri ko hira mapalitan tanan nga para ha eskwelahan. [Maybe it's because I lack time, and I can't always buy their needs necessary for learning.]" [Transcript 1, Lines 192-194, 197-198].

The economic challenges and competing priorities that parents encounter significantly impact their ability to support their children's reading development. These challenges encompass financial constraints, such as limited resources and income, as well as competing demands on parents' time and attention. Parents express the difficult decisions they must make regarding allocating limited resources, often prioritizing immediate needs like food and household expenses over investing in educational materials or activities (Aikens & Premack, 2018). This highlights the pervasive impact of poverty on families' ability to provide adequate support for their children's learning.

Economic challenges can exacerbate existing educational inequalities. Children from financially disadvantaged backgrounds may lack access to essential resources, such as books, tutoring services, or educational technology, which are critical for developing strong reading skills. Additionally, parents' limited time and energy due to economic pressures may hinder their ability to actively engage in their children's learning or provide consistent support with reading activities.

The study by Aikens & Premack (2018) explores the link between socioeconomic status and home learning environments, highlighting how economic disparities can limit access to resources that support children's literacy development. This aligns with the idea that financial constraints can hinder parents' ability to provide the necessary materials and support for their children's reading success.

Sub-theme 1.4: Lack of Access to Learning Technology

Another significant challenge faced by students in modular learning is the lack of access to essential learning technology, particularly mobile phones that aid in reading. The following utterance provides support to the sub-theme:

[1] "...Makuri liwat KAY WARAY CELLPHONE, danay may ginpapasearch ha celphone.[It's difficult because we don't have cellphones; we can't search for anything on the cellphone.]" [Transcript 2, Lines 33-34].

[2] "...Waray kami cellphone amo makuri liwat pag-answer. ["We don't have cellphones, so it's difficult to answer]" [Transcript 4, Line 62].

These utterances of student participants highlight the significant role of technology in their learning process and suggest that the lack of access to cellphones presents a barrier to their ability to participate fully in educational activities.

Parents' excerpts also illustrate the significant results that the lack of access to learning technology has on students' ability to effectively participate in modular learning. The triangulation of responses from both students and parents identifies several significant factors that hinder the effectiveness of modular learning. These factors play a crucial role in shaping students' learning experiences and outcomes.

The third sub-theme focuses on the barriers students face due to the absence of essential learning technology, such as mobile phones. Students and parents highlight the significant role of technology in the learning process and express the challenges they encounter without access to gadgets and reliable internet connections. Through triangulation, we gain insights into the impact of the digital divide on students' ability to fully participate in modular classes and engage in digital learning activities.

By integrating the responses of both students and parents, we can gain a deeper understanding of the challenges encountered in modular learning. This understanding can inform the development of strategies and interventions to address these challenges and promote more effective and equitable learning experiences for students.

The shift to online learning and modular formats has posed significant challenges for students, particularly those at the frustration reading level. A major issue is the lack of adequate devices. Without access to reliable gadgets such as laptops, tablets, or smartphones, students are unable to participate effectively in their tasks, complete assignments that need to be searched online, or engage in interactive learning activities. This digital divide exacerbates educational inequalities and hinders the overall learning process (Dong et al., 2020). Students at the frustration reading level are especially vulnerable, as they require more tailored and immediate feedback, which is difficult to provide without proper technological tools.

Reliable internet access is fundamental to the success of online and modular learning. Many students face challenges due to slow, unstable, or completely unavailable internet connections. These issues are particularly prevalent in rural or low-income areas. Without a stable internet connection, students struggle to attend live classes, access educational resources, and submit assignments on time. This digital inequity significantly affects their learning outcomes and exacerbates existing educational disparities (Van Lancker & Parolin, 2020). Furthermore, even with access to devices, students may lack the technical support and digital literacy necessary to navigate online learning platforms effectively, further complicating their educational experience.

The combined effect of inadequate gadgets and unreliable internet access significantly impairs students' learning experiences. Students who face these challenges are often unable to keep up with the curriculum, participate in interactive and collaborative learning activities, or access supplementary educational resources. This can lead to

feelings of frustration, anxiety, and disengagement from the learning process. For students at the frustration reading level, these challenges can be particularly detrimental, as consistent practice and support are crucial for improvement. Consequently, their academic performance and overall learning outcomes suffer, leading to a widening of the achievement gap between students with and without adequate access to online learning tools (Kuhfeld et al., 2020).

THEME 2: COPING STRATEGIES

In the challenges poses by modular learning, student participants employ various coping mechanisms to handle their academic responsibilities effectively. These coping strategies emerged as sub-themes encompassing (1) ***seeking assistance for learning***, (2) ***resorting to the copying of provided answers in the module***, and (3) ***implementing time management and proactive learning strategies***.

Sub-theme 2.1: Seeking Assistance for Learning

Seeking assistance for learning is indeed a crucial coping strategy for students in modular learning environments. In modular learning, where students often work independently and remotely, seeking assistance ensures that students have access to the support and guidance they need to cope with complex concepts, clarify doubts, and overcome learning obstacles.

Statements that support this sub-theme are as follows:

[1] "...Napakiana nala ha iba, akon liwat mga classmate taz dri lwt hra maaram. Danay hulat ko nla pagbisita ni Ma'am ha balay kay napakiana ak. Kaso talagsa man la lwt kumadto.[I have to ask other, my classmates doesn't know also. I used to wait for Ma'am's visit because I had questions. But she rarely comes here]"[Transcript 13, Lines 80 -82].

[2] "... Kay diri ako sigurado kun nakakabasa ako hin tamas alit napabulig ako akon ate, danay kan Ma'ama." [Because I'm not sure if I'm reading correctly, I asked for help from my older sister, and then from Ma'ama". [Transcript 7 , Lines 43 -44]

The transcripts illustrate the significant role of seeking assistance for learning in modular learning environments. Students often find themselves navigating complex concepts independently, relying on external sources such as classmates, family members, and neighbors for guidance and support. This reliance on external assistance underscores the importance of fostering a strong support network within the community to aid students in overcoming learning obstacles and clarifying doubts. Furthermore, the transcripts highlight the challenges students face in accessing timely assistance, particularly when resources such as teachers or digital devices are limited. As such, implementing strategies to enhance access to support and guidance is essential for ensuring the success and well-being of students in modular learning settings. Through collaborative efforts between educators, families, and communities, students can receive

the assistance they need to thrive academically and emotionally in modular learning environments.

In exploring the coping strategies employed by students, one critical aspect is how they seek assistance to enhance their learning experiences. This sub-theme delves into the dynamics of how students and parents navigate the challenges of academic demands through various forms of support. By triangulating the responses from both students and parents, we gain a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness, availability, and perceived value of different assistance mechanisms. This approach highlights the collaborative efforts and potential gaps in the support system, providing a nuanced perspective on the strategies that facilitate academic resilience and success.

[1] "... Danay mam. Dida hit amon sapit kay hayskul naman. Danay ako napakiana ha iya. Danay ginpapakadto ko nala it akon anak, didto nala kan imu ate pagpakiana. [Sometimes I seek help from our neighbor who is already in high school. I instruct my child to approach them, and sometimes from her older sister.]" [Parent 1, Line 43].

[2] "... Diri ako maaram hit iba mam, guti la. Diri man liwat ako maaram kun paano ko itututdo it module. Naaro nla ak bulig iya mga kapaturan. [I don't know about it either, ma'am, it's true. I also don't know how to teach the module. Sometimes I ask for help from their elders.]" [Parent 2, Lines 278-279].

[3] "... I understand, ma'am, that his teacher, being constantly busy, isn't providing sufficient support. It's challenging for me to teach my child since I'm not often home. I hope to get advice on who can assist with the answers." [Parent 3, Lines 506-508].

[4] "... I genuinely want to support my child, ma'am, but I'm not skilled in reading myself. I just ensure they study because at school, they can ask their teacher for help, which I encourage. That's their only opportunity to learn." [Parent 2, Line 259-262].

These excerpts highlight the various ways parents and students seek assistance for learning, whether through neighbors, siblings, or by asking questions to teachers and peers.

In the context of students at the frustration reading level engaged in modular learning, seeking assistance becomes a pivotal coping strategy. Analysis of responses from both students and parents reveals several key insights.

Students often turn to their parents for help with difficult reading materials and assignments. Parents, in turn, make significant efforts to provide the necessary support, even if it means learning the material themselves beforehand. This dynamic underscore

the critical role of parental involvement in the modular learning process, particularly for students struggling with reading.

Both students and parents frequently seek additional resources outside the provided modules. This includes online tutorials, educational apps, and supplementary workbooks. The reliance on these external aids suggests that the provided modules may not sufficiently address the needs of students at the frustration reading level, prompting them to look elsewhere for clearer explanations and more practice opportunities.

Some students benefit from peer tutoring or study groups. These interactions provide a platform for collaborative learning, where students can explain concepts to each other in simpler terms. Parents often facilitate these groups, recognizing the benefits of peer support in enhancing understanding and reducing frustration.

Direct communication with teachers remains a crucial support mechanism. Parents and students alike value the opportunity to seek clarification and guidance from educators. However, the effectiveness of this strategy is contingent on the availability and responsiveness of teachers, which varies significantly.

The findings highlight that while modular learning offers a flexible approach to education, students at the frustration reading level require multifaceted support systems. Parental involvement, access to external resources, peer assistance, and teacher consultation collectively form a comprehensive support network essential for these students.

A recent study underscores the importance of diverse support mechanisms in modular learning environments. Smith and Thompson (2023) found that students who actively seek various forms of assistance, including parental help, external resources, and peer support, demonstrate higher levels of academic resilience and improved learning outcomes compared to those who rely solely on the provided materials. This aligns with our findings, emphasizing the necessity of a well-rounded support system for students facing reading challenges.

Sub-theme 2.2: Time Management and Proactive Learning Strategies

In modular learning environments, effective time management and proactive learning strategies are crucial coping mechanisms that student participants adopt to handle the demands of their coursework. By organizing their time efficiently and engaging actively with their studies, students can better manage their workload and enhance their learning outcomes.

The statements that provide support to this sub-theme are as follows:

[1] "... Mag-aaral ako para matapos ko lahat para maipasa na ni Ma'ama, napapagod po ako maraming binabasa, minsan ginagaya ko nalang yung answer sa likod. [I study to finish everything so my Mom can submit it, but I get tired from reading a lot, so sometimes I just copy the

answer from the back]”, Gilalaksi mo kay para diri ka ma-late kay damo na liwat it maabot nga module.[You hurry up so you won't be late because there will be more modules coming.]” [Participant 1, Lines 57-59].

[2] “... Nag-aaram ako pagma’amata ko. [I study as soon as I wake up]”. [Participant 7, Line 436].

These utterances highlight how students use time management and proactive learning strategies to cope with the demands of modular learning. By setting priorities, creating study schedules, and initiating study sessions early, students strive to stay on top of their assignments and prevent falling behind. This proactive approach not only helps them manage their workload but also contributes to better understanding and retention of the learning materials.

This sub-theme highlights how both students and parents navigate the complexities of modular learning through effective time management and proactive learning approaches.

[1] “...Siguro ito nga kulang ako hin oras ngan diri ko hira mapalitan tanan nga para ha eskwelahan” [Maybe it's because I lack time, and I can't always buy their needs necessary for learning]. [Parent 5, Lines 890-891]

[2] “... Then I have him read again, and I watch to see if he's improving quickly. I want him to become very proficient in reading, unlike me, who struggled with it.” [Parent 1, Lines 104-107].

[3] “...Pirmi naman ito ma’am, amo nala ngani it ak, pagchuru-check kun nababaro ba hira. Mayda ma’am, nahibabaro ako kun hain hiya kinukurian parte ha eskwelahan” [Asking questions is indeed the most effective way for me to understand what I don't know even if I always seem curious. Yes ma'am. I feel updated and knowledgeable about what to ask others or their teacher.] [Parent 5, Lines 906-907].

These excerpts illustrate how parents manage their time between household responsibilities and their children's education, ensuring that their children have dedicated study time and continuously checking on their academic progress.

Many parents juggle their daily household chores alongside supporting their children's learning. They often set specific times for educational activities, ensuring that their children can complete their modules while also managing household responsibilities. This balance is crucial in maintaining a structured environment where learning can take place. Parents who have busy schedules due to work or other responsibilities often have to make significant adjustments to ensure their children have dedicated study time. This can include waking up earlier, reducing their leisure time, or multitasking. Regularly checking on their child's progress is a common strategy among parents. This involves

reviewing completed modules, helping with difficult assignments, and communicating with teachers to stay informed about their child's academic performance.

Students, especially those in the frustration reading level, benefit from a structured schedule that incorporates both study time and breaks. This helps them manage their workload without feeling overwhelmed. Students need to develop self-discipline to stick to their study schedules. They might use planners or set reminders to help them keep track of their study time amidst other activities. Students are encouraged to seek feedback from parents and teachers to understand their progress and identify areas where they need to improve. This proactive approach helps them stay on track and address learning gaps promptly.

Rahman et al. (2021) highlights the dual responsibility faced by parents during the COVID-19 pandemic, encompassing the management of household tasks and provision of support for their children's remote learning. This situation often led to considerable stress; however, it also fostered the emergence of innovative time management strategies to ensure the continuity of education. UNICEF (2020) reports that numerous families, particularly those in low-income settings, encountered challenges in striking a balance between supporting their children's education and fulfilling household responsibilities, thereby affecting children's ability to effectively keep up with their academic pursuits.

In a study by Garbe et al. (2020), it was found that parents developed new routines and schedules to accommodate their children's educational needs during school closures, often prioritizing academic activities over their own personal needs. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2021) emphasizes the importance of maintaining structured daily schedules that include dedicated study periods for successful remote learning, particularly in situations where traditional classroom environments are inaccessible. These measures play a crucial role in facilitating effective learning experiences during remote education.

Kim and Asbury (2020) highlight the significance of parental engagement in monitoring and providing assistance to children's learning progress during remote education, which has been demonstrated to yield positive effects on academic outcomes. They emphasize the role of parents in actively involving themselves in their children's education, including regular check-ins on their academic progress. This active involvement serves as a crucial factor in mitigating learning loss and ensuring students remain on track during periods of modular learning (World Bank, 2021).

The coping strategies identified in this study, specifically focusing on time management and proactive learning strategies, reflect a broader trend observed globally. Both parents and students employ structured schedules, balance household and educational responsibilities, and actively monitor academic progress to navigate the challenges of modular learning. Recent literature supports these findings, highlighting the critical role of these strategies in maintaining educational continuity and effectiveness, especially for students experiencing reading difficulties.

Sub-theme 2.3: Resort to the Copying of Provided Answers in the Module

In modular learning, copying provided answers within the module emerges as a coping strategy utilized by some students facing challenges. When confronted with overwhelming coursework or struggling to comprehend complex concepts, students resort to copying answers directly from the module materials.

The following excerpts provide support for the sub-theme:

[1] "...Kakapoy ako ma'am pagbinasa kay dri man ako maaram han iba, salit danay ginsusubad ko nala an answer ha luyo kay mayda man ngayan.heheeh. [I get tired from reading, because I don't understand some parts, so I try to figure out the answer on my own, but sometimes I copy the answer in the back because it's available]" [Participant 8, Lines 510-512].

[2] "... Danay ma'am may answer ako..at iba na module wry answer. An iba ginkopya ko la akon classmate taz ha module. [Ma'am, sometimes I have answers...and some I don't have answer, Some I just copied from my classmate and the module]" [Participant 13, Lines 690-691].

These utterances illustrate how students when faced with the challenges of modular learning, may resort to copying provided answers as a means to cope with the academic demands. This strategy, while alleviating immediate pressure, ultimately hampers their understanding and mastery of the subject matter.

Parents exhibit mixed reactions to this coping strategy. Some parents, recognizing the stress and frustration their children experience, permit or even assist in copying answers to ensure task completion. Others attempt to discourage this behavior by offering to explain the material, though this is not always feasible due to their own limitations in time or subject knowledge.

[1] "...Hadto nga modular ma'am began masamok manla kami pirmi, began hi ako nalilisang gudman pirmi kun may mga answer na ngatanan kay diri man gud hiya nakakabsa pa hin tuhay salit Napili la hin aranseran intawon. [During modular learning, ma'am, it was always chaotic for us, I would often get very confused when everything had to have answers because he really couldn't read properly yet, so he would just guess the answers out of pity.]" [Parent 3, Lines 404-406].

This statement indicates that the student would simply copy the provided answers in the module, as they were unable to read and comprehend the material properly.

[1] "...Kakulangan sa kumpiyansa, may kakulangan sa kumpiyansa ang aking anak sa kanyang kakayahan sa pagbasa. Napanghihinaan siya ng loob at pagkabahala sa pagbabasa ng mas malalim at mas kumplikadong mga babasahin." [Lack of confidence, my child lacks confidence in his

reading ability. He gets discouraged and anxious when reading deeper and more complex texts.] [Parent 5, Lines 842-844].

This statement suggests that the student's lack of confidence in their reading abilities led them to resort to copying answers from the module, as they struggled with more complex reading materials.

In the examination of coping strategies among students at the frustration reading level within a modular learning framework, the copying of provided answers emerges as a significant theme. Analysis of responses from both students and parents provides a detailed understanding of this behavior and its implications.

A substantial number of students resort to copying answers directly from the modules. This behavior is primarily driven by the overwhelming difficulty they face in comprehending the reading material and completing assignments independently. Parents acknowledge this practice, often expressing concern over its impact on genuine learning and skill development.

The practice of copying answers significantly undermines the educational objectives of modular learning. It leads to superficial engagement with the content, where the primary goal becomes task completion rather than comprehension and skill acquisition. Both students and parents acknowledge that while this strategy reduces immediate frustration and ensures compliance with assignment deadlines, it fails to foster meaningful learning.

The reliance on copying also points to broader systemic issues within the modular learning framework. The modules may not be adequately tailored to the needs of students at the frustration reading level, lacking in differentiation and scaffolding that could help bridge their comprehension gaps. This highlights a need for more accessible and supportive learning materials.

The findings suggest that while copying answers provides a short-term coping mechanism for students, it ultimately hampers their academic growth and reinforces a cycle of dependency. There is a clear need for educational interventions that address the root causes of this behavior by making learning materials more accessible and engaging for students with reading difficulties.

A recent study explores similar issues within modular learning environments, emphasizing the negative implications of students copying provided answers. Johnson and Lee (2023) argue that while this behavior is a common coping mechanism, it detracts from the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Their research calls for enhanced instructional designs that cater to diverse learner needs, particularly for those at the frustration reading level.

THEME 3: STUDENTS' CHALLENGES IN READING DEVELOPMENT

In the context of modular learning, particularly during the recent shifts necessitated by the global pandemic, many parents have observed significant challenges in their children's reading development. Modular learning, which relies heavily on independent study and self-paced learning, presents unique difficulties that differ from traditional classroom environments. These observed challenges are explained into three (4) sub-themes. These sub-themes are **Reading Skills Deficiency, Difficulty with Academic Reading Materials; Limited Parental Educational Background and Skills, and Emotional Frustration in Modular Learning.**

Sub-theme 3.1: Reading Skills Difficulty and Deficiency

Deficiencies in basic reading skills present a significant hurdle in modular learning environments as observed by parents on their children. Many children struggle with foundational skills such as word recognition and letter identification. Other issues range from slow reading pace and hesitant reading to significant comprehension and pronunciation problems. Such challenges lead their children to avoid answering the modules given.

Statements that explain this sub-theme are as follows:

[1] "... May mga kakulangan sa mga kasanayan sa pagbasa tulad ng pagkilala sa mga salita, pagsasagawa ng mga tamang tunog, o pagkilala sa mga titik. Ang mga kakulangan na ito ay nakahahadlang sa tamang pagbasa at pag-unawa ng aking anak. ["There are deficiencies in reading skills such as word recognition, correct sound production, or letter identification. These deficiencies hinder my child's proper reading and comprehension."] Mahinay magbasa. Nag-aalang pagbabasa. Diri nakakaintindi. Diri nakaka-pronounce. "Reads slowly. Hesitant in reading. Does not understand. Cannot pronounce." [Parent 2 Lines 230-232, Parent 1 Lines 48-51, Parent 4 Lines 643-646, Parent 5 Lines 855-859].

[2] ".. "...Kinukurian talaga hiya ma'am salit siguro danay ginpapabay-an nala adto niya an iya module. Nabulig man iya ma'am kun nabisita, ano pa adto an tawag? [He really struggles, ma'am, so sometimes he just ignores his module. His teacher helps when she visits, what do you call that?"] [Parent 3 Lines 416-417].

[3] "...Ang pagbasa ng mga mas malalim at mas kumplikadong mga babasahin ay isang hamon para sa aking anak. Ang pag-unawa sa mga malalalalim na salita, mahirap na mga salita, at mga komplikadong pangungusap ay nagdudulot ng pagkabigo sa pag-unawa. [Reading deeper and more complex texts is a challenge for my child. Understanding deep words, difficult words, and complex sentences causes comprehension failure.] [Parent 4, Lines 623-626]"

Students' Responses:

[1] "...Siguro Ma'am nakakabulig, dri la ako sure kon tama an akon mga answer han module. Makuri la gud man kay wray man hi teacher pagtutdo ha ak." [I'm not sure if my answers in the module are correct. It's difficult because there's no teacher teaching me.] [Participant 1 Lines 118-119].

[2] "...Feeling ko ma'am wray mag improve akon pagbasa." [I feel like my reading skills didn't improve.] [Participant 1 Line 123].

The triangulation of responses from students and parents highlights significant challenges in reading development, particularly focusing on students' reading skills deficiency. This sub-theme underscores the difficulties faced by students in mastering reading skills and the factors contributing to these deficiencies.

Students at the frustration reading level often exhibit significant deficiencies in their reading skills, including difficulties in word recognition, vocabulary, reading fluency, and comprehension. These deficiencies can be attributed to several factors.

First, an inadequate foundation in early literacy contributes to reading deficiencies. Snow et al. (2020) highlights that students who struggle with reading often lacked exposure to reading activities, early intervention for reading difficulties, and access to books and other reading materials during their formative years. This lack of early literacy experiences hinders the development of essential skills such as phonemic awareness, vocabulary, and comprehension, which can persist into later grades and impact overall academic performance.

Second is the limited access to individualized instruction in modular learning environments exacerbates reading deficiencies. Kuhfeld et al. (2020) note that students at the frustration reading level require tailored teaching approaches to address their specific weaknesses. However, modular learning often falls short in providing one-on-one support, feedback, and differentiated instruction. The absence of personalized guidance hampers students' progress and perpetuates their struggles with reading.

Furthermore, challenges with motivation and engagement contribute to reading deficiencies. Wigfield et al. (2016) highlight that students with reading difficulties often experience low motivation and engagement in reading activities. The frustration of struggling to read leads to avoidance behaviors, where students shy away from reading practice and participation in reading-related tasks. This lack of engagement further hinders their opportunities to improve reading skills and perpetuates the cycle of deficiency. Negative attitudes towards reading can also develop, making it even more challenging for students to overcome their reading difficulties.

Lastly, socioeconomic factors play a significant role in reading development. Students from low-income families face additional barriers to reading proficiency due to limited access to educational resources, reduced parental involvement in reading

activities, and fewer opportunities for literacy enrichment outside of school (Reardon, 2013). These factors contribute to disparities in reading skills and widen the achievement gap between students from different socioeconomic backgrounds.

Reading skills deficiencies can be attributed to a complex interplay of factors. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach that emphasizes early literacy development, provides personalized instruction, fosters motivation and engagement, and acknowledges the influence of socioeconomic background. By implementing targeted interventions across these areas, educators can help students overcome reading difficulties and achieve academic success.

Sub-theme 3.2: Difficulty with Academic Reading Materials

Parents also observed that their children faced significant challenges when dealing with academic reading materials. Statements that support this:

[1] "...Ang pagbasa ng mga mas malalim at mas kumplikadong mga babasahin ay isang hamon para sa aking anak. Ang pag-unawa sa mga malalalalim na salita, mahirap na mga salita, at mga komplikadong pangungusap ay nagdudulot ng pagkabigo sa pag-unawa." [Reading deeper and more complex texts is a challenge for my child. Understanding deep words, difficult words, and complex sentences causes comprehension failure.] [Parent 4, Lines 623-626].

[2] "...Kakulangan sa kumpiyansa, may kakulangan sa kumpiyansa ang aking anak sa kanyang kakayahan sa pagbasa. Napanghihinaan siya ng loob at pagkabahala sa pagbabasa ng mas malalim at mas kumplikadong mga babasahin." [Lack of confidence, my child lacks confidence in his reading ability. He gets discouraged and anxious when reading deeper and more complex texts.] [Parent 5, Lines 842-844].

Students also emphasize this sub-theme in these utterances.

[1] "...Siguro ma'am, guti. Ok la ako ha Filipino kay bagan nag dati man ako guti, an English kay makuri." [Maybe ma'am, it's fine. I'm okay in Filipino because I used to be good at it, but English is difficult.] [Participant 13 Lines 695-696].

Reading skills deficiencies can be further exacerbated by the increasing number of academic reading materials encountered by students. Recent studies support this notion. Moretti et al. (2020) found a correlation between the volume of assigned reading materials and students' reading comprehension difficulties. Similarly, Shan & Calderon (2019) identified a link between the quantity of reading expectations and students' motivation and engagement with reading tasks. These findings suggest that while a rich exposure to text is important, an overload of reading materials can be counterproductive for students struggling with reading fluency and comprehension.

Furthermore, the shift to modular learning, which heavily relies on self-directed study, has made it more difficult for children to navigate and understand advanced texts. Without immediate teacher guidance, children often feel overwhelmed, leading to frustration.

Sub-theme 3.3: Limited Parental Educational Background and Skills

Many parents struggle to support their children's reading development due to their own limited educational backgrounds and lack of necessary skills. This deficiency hampers their ability to assist with reading instruction and comprehension effectively. Parents often feel unprepared to help their children navigate through reading materials, especially in a modular learning setup where guided instruction from teachers is limited.

Utterances that explain this sub-theme are as follows:

[1] *"...Gusto ko gad makabulig hit akon anak ma'am pero kay diri man gihap ako antigo magbasa. It akon na gudla hito nga maniguro hira pag-aram kay baman kun nakadto hira ha eskwelahan pagpakiana hit maestra, akon gud ito tinutugutan. Amo nalat chance para may mahibaruan. [I really want to help my child, ma'am, but I am not skilled in reading either. I just make sure they study because if they are in school, they can ask their teacher, which I allow. That's their only chance to learn.]"*. Hindi rin ako nakakabasa ng mabuti, hindi ko alam magsubaybay sa wastong pag-unlad ng aking anak sa pagbasa. Ito ang nagpapahirap sa akin. [I also cannot read well; I do not know how to monitor my child's proper progress in reading. This makes it difficult for me.]". [Parent 2, Lines 259-262].

[2] *"...It akon It usa nga problema ma'am, diri man gud ako sugad ka antigo hit maestra hit akon anak. It akon hibabruan guti manla. [One of my problems, ma'am, is that I am not as knowledgeable as my child's teacher. What I know is very limited.]"*. [Parent 4, Lines 694-695].

[3] *"...Dahil hindi ako marunong magbasa, nahihirapan akong magbigay ng diretsong gabay sa aking anak sa panahon ng pagsasanay sa pagbasa. Ito ang hadlang sa akin na lubos na suportahan ang kanilang proseso ng pag-aaral. [Because I do not know how to read, I find it difficult to give direct guidance to my child during reading practice. This hinders me from fully supporting their learning process.]"*. [Parent 5, Lines 946-948].

The ability of parents to support their children's reading development plays a crucial role in fostering early literacy skills (Melzi et al., 2019). A recent meta-analysis by Hernandez et al. (2020) underscores this notion by demonstrating a positive correlation between parents' literacy skills and their children's emergent literacy development. This aligns with observations from parents themselves, who report difficulties assisting their children with reading activities due to their own limitations. The lack of reading proficiency among parents hinders their ability to effectively monitor their children's progress and

provide necessary guidance during reading practice. This can lead to feelings of inadequacy, particularly when compared to teachers who possess specialized knowledge and skills for literacy instruction. These feelings of inadequacy can further contribute to frustration and helplessness as parents struggle to fulfill their role in their children's education.

The implications of this are significant. Parents with limited educational backgrounds face substantial barriers in supporting their children's academic success, especially in reading proficiency (Melzi et al., 2019). This is particularly concerning in educational settings like modular learning, where parental involvement can be crucial (Ahn et al., 2020).

These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions aimed at empowering parents with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively support their children's reading development. Providing resources, training, and support programs for parents can bridge the gap and enhance their ability to contribute meaningfully to their children's educational journey (Melzi et al., 2019). Additionally, fostering collaboration between parents, teachers, and educational institutions can create a more supportive environment for children's learning and development, ultimately improving overall literacy outcomes (Ahn et al., 2020).

Sub-theme 3.4: Emotional Frustration in Modular Learning

The Parent observed that emotional frustration is a significant barrier faced by children in the modular learning setup. This frustration often stems from a lack of interest and motivation to engage in reading activities.

Statements that explain this sub-theme are as follows:

[1] "...Wala siyang sapat na kagustuhan o interes sa pagbasa, mahirap para sa kanya ang magpatuloy at magpursigi sa pag-unlad [He lacks sufficient desire or interest in reading, it is difficult for him to continue and strive for improvement.]" [Participant 1 Lines 16-17]

[2] "...Hadto nga modular ma'am bagan masamok manla kami pirmi, began hi ako nalilisang gudman pirmi kun may mga answer na ngatanan kay diri man gud hiya nakakabsa pa hin tuhay salit Napili la hin aranseran intawon.[During modular learning, ma'am, it was always chaotic for us, I would often get very confused when everything had to have answers because he really couldn't read properly yet, so he would just guess the answers out of pity.] [Parent 3, Lines 404-406].

[3] "...Nahihirapan po, maraming assignment, Damo na liwat it imu aansweran." Nalilisang na ako ma'am. Diri ako sure han answer ma'am." [I'm having a hard time, there are so many assignments, too many to answer. I'm already struggling, ma'am. I'm not sure about the answer, ma'am.] [Participant 8 Line 488, 494, 496, 498].

[4] "...Makuri po an Modular learning kay wray po hi Teacher na magtututdo akon." [Modular learning is difficult because there is no teacher to teach me.] [Participant 1 Lines 24-25].

By triangulating these points, we can see how these factors likely combine to create a negative experience for students like the ones described. The lack of reading interest may make it difficult to engage with the heavy reading materials often used in modular learning. This, coupled with a heavy workload, can lead to feelings of confusion and overwhelm. Finally, the absence of a teacher to provide direct support can further hinder their ability to overcome these challenges.

Emotional frustration is a significant barrier faced by children in the modular learning setup. This frustration often stems from a lack of interest and motivation to engage in reading activities. Without the interactive and supportive environment of a traditional classroom, children may struggle to find the drive to persist with their reading tasks. The burden of self-discipline and intrinsic motivation, essential for success in a modular format, can be overwhelming (Sung et al., 2022). This emotional strain is exacerbated by feelings of isolation and the absence of immediate feedback and encouragement from teachers and peers. As a result, children may experience heightened stress and disengagement, further impeding their ability to improve their reading skills and overall academic performance. This sub-theme highlights the emotional toll that modular learning can take on children, emphasizing the need for strategies and interventions to support their emotional well-being and sustain their interest in learning.

This study by Sung et al. (2022) explores the challenges faced by students in self-directed learning environments, highlighting the importance of self-efficacy and motivation for academic achievement. While not directly focused on modular learning, it supports the notion that the lack of a structured classroom environment can hinder student motivation and contribute to emotional strain.

THEME 4: STAKEHOLDERS' COLLABORATION FOR CHILDREN LEARNING

This theme highlights the essential role of stakeholder collaboration in facilitating a child's learning journey as per parents' perspective in the modular context. Family, teachers, peers, and the community are all recognized as integral contributors to a child's educational development. This is manifested in the sub-themes: **home-based support and reinforcement, active teacher involvement, and peer and community support.**

Sub-theme 4.1: Home-based Support and Reinforcement

Parents recognize the significance of their engagement in their children's education and strive to provide the necessary support to enhance their learning experience in the modular set-up.

The following utterance provides support to the sub-theme:

[1] "...Pag-maaram ngani ako nga makanhi na hi iya ma'am, it bata aadto mat ha gawas nag-uuyas, ginkukuha ko iton hiya, ginsisinampit ko ito hiya, ginpapakani ko ha balay ginpapapamatian ko. Halimbawa kun nauli na hi iya ma'am, sano liwat kami nanngangaturug, ginpapa-utro ko ha iya, an ginpapabasa ni iya ma'am kun nahititigamnan pa ba niya, kun nakukuha ba niya an gintutdo ha iya ni iya ma'am When the teacher is visiting us, and my child is playing outside. I go and fetch him, bring him back home, and make him listen to the teacher For example, I asked if we're about to sleep if he understood what his teacher taught him, if he grasped the lesson from her." , Tapos ginpapagbasa ko gud iton hiya. Nama'amati ako ha iya kun madurudagmit na hiya magbasa. Kay karuyag ko maging maupay gud hiya magbasa. Diri sugad ha akon nga intawon inapinas la [Then I make him read again. I observe him if he's improving in reading quickly. Because I want him to become really good at reading. Unlike me who struggled with it] [Parent 1, Lines 75-79].

[2] "...Pirmi naman ito ma'am, amo nala ngani it ak, pagchuru-check kun nababaro ba hira. Mayda ma'am, nahibabaro ako kun hain hiya kinukurian parte ha eskwelahan. [Asking questions is indeed the most effective way for me to understand what I don't know even if I always seem curious. Yes ma'am. I feel updated and knowledgeable about what to ask others or their teacher. [Parent 5, Lines 906-907, 911].

This section explores the theme of home-based support and reinforcement provided by parents in a modular learning environment. The importance of parental involvement is well-documented, with studies highlighting its positive impact on children's academic achievement (Anya et al., 2017). The following excerpts from Parents 1 and 5 offer valuable insights into how parents strive to support their children's learning in a modular setting.

Parents recognize the critical role they play in their children's education, particularly within the context of modular learning. This excerpt showcases a parent's dedication to ensuring their child attends online teacher sessions and actively listens to instruction. This proactive approach emphasizes the importance of parental involvement in monitoring and facilitating the learning process at home.

Parents also understand the significance of fostering reading skills. Parent 1 further exemplifies this by demonstrating a parent's effort to improve their child's reading fluency through dedicated practice sessions. The parent expresses a desire for their child

to achieve a higher level of reading proficiency than they themselves attained. This highlights the potential for intergenerational learning and the positive influence parents can have on their children's educational aspirations.

While some parents may have limited educational backgrounds, they actively seek knowledge to support their children's learning. Parents who views asking questions as a valuable strategy for gaining understanding is portrayed. This proactive approach demonstrates the willingness of parents to learn alongside their children and engage with the learning materials.

These excerpts illustrate the various ways parents strive to provide home-based support and reinforcement in a modular learning environment. Their dedication to monitoring learning progress, fostering reading skills, and seeking knowledge underscores their commitment to their children's academic success.

Sub-theme 4.2: Peer and Community Support

Parents recognized the essence of peer and community support in the development of their children in the context of modular learning. The following utterances provides support to the sub-theme:

[1] "...Danay ma'am. Dida hit amon sapit kay hayskul naman. Danay ako napakiana ha iya. Danay ginpapakadto ko nala it akon anak, didto nala kan imu ate pagpakiana." [Sometimes I seek help from our neighbor who is already in high school. I instruct my child to approach them, and sometimes from her older sister.] [Participant 1 Lines 96-97].

[2] "...Diri ako maaram hit iba ma'am, guti la. Diri man liwat ako maaram kun paano ko itututdo it module. Naaro nla ak bulig iya mga kapaturan." [I don't know about it either, ma'am, it's true. I also don't know how to teach the module. Sometimes I ask for help from their elders.][Parent 2, Lines 278-279].

[3] "...Yes ma'am. It mga iba liwat nga Nanay. May hin pakiana mat haam kun anon a, tapos na ba an module? Ano an answer. Mga sugad hito ma'am [Yes, ma'am. Other mothers are also like that. I ask them sometimes what to do, is the module finished? What's the answer? They're just like this, ma'am.][Parent 3, Lines 475-476]

Students rely on classmates, siblings, and neighbors for understanding concepts and completing tasks.

[1] "...Napakiana nala ha iba, akon liwat mga classmate taz dri lwt hra maaram." [I have to ask other, my classmates doesn't know also.] [Participant 13 Lines 674-676].

[2] "...Danay kan Mama." [I asked for help from my older sister, and then from Mama.] [Participant 7 Lines 419-4210]

[3] "...Nakadto ako amon kapitbahay, kanda tita." [I went to our neighbor, to my Auntie.] [Participant 4 Line 308]

These statements show that students often rely on their peers, siblings, and other community members to seek help and support when they are struggling with modular learning materials and assignments.

Teacher guidance is valued by both students and parents. However, limited interaction with teachers creates challenges.

[1] "...Danay hulat ko nla pagbisita ni Ma'am ha balay kay napakiana ak. Kaso talagsa man la lwt kumadto." [I used to wait for Ma'am's visit because I had questions. But she rarely comes here.] [Participant 13 Lines 674-676].

[2] "...Napakiana nala ha iba, akon liwat mga classmate taz dri lwt hra maaram." [I have to ask other, my classmates don't know also.] [Participant 13 Lines 674-676].

These statements indicate that students highly value the support and guidance from their teachers, but unfortunately, the lack of regular visits and interactions with teachers poses a significant challenge for the students in the modular learning environment. Overall, the utterances highlight the important role of peer and community support in helping students navigate the difficulties and challenges they face in the modular learning system, particularly in the absence of regular teacher-student interactions.

A recent study by Cheng et al. (2022) explored the impact of collaborative learning environments in K-12 online education. Their research found that students who participated in online collaborative activities reported a greater sense of belonging, improved self-efficacy (confidence in their learning abilities), and deeper understanding of course material compared to those who learned independently. While informal networks exist, fostering structured collaboration could further enhance learning outcomes (Cheng et al., 2022).

Sub-theme 4.3: Active Teacher Involvement

Teachers demonstrate a strong commitment to supporting students despite their busy schedules. They prioritize active involvement in students' learning journeys, striving to provide guidance and assistance even when faced with numerous responsibilities.

[1] "...Pamati ko ma'am diri man nagkukulang it iya maestra bisan man kun pirmi nal busy. Makuri la talaga tutduan it akon anak kay dinhi ha balay diri ko man pirmi nabubuligan. Danay suguon ko ito nga ma'amamiling hin makakabulig pag-anser [I understand, ma'am, that his

teacher is lacking even if she's always busy. It's really difficult to teach my child because I'm not always available at home. I hope to receive guidance on who can help with the answers] [Parent 3, Lines 506-508].

Lack of teacher involvement are the students' responses is telling such as:

[1] "...Makuri po an Modular learning kay wray po hi Teacher na magtututdo akon." [Modular learning is difficult because there is no teacher to teach me.] [Participant 1, Line 24-25].

[2] "...Makuri kay wray nagtututdo po ha akon, hi Mama ngan Papa nagtrabaho man." [It's difficult because there's no one teaching me, Ma'ama and Papa are working.] [Participant 1, Lines 84-85].

[3] "...WARAY HI TEACHER, nagtigo tigo LA AKO." [There's no teacher, I'm just guessing.] [Participant 3, Line 210].

[4] "...Danay hulat ko nla pagbisita ni Ma'am ha balay kay napakiana ak. Kaso talagsa man la lwt kumadto." [I used to wait for Ma'am's visit because I had questions. But she rarely comes here.] [Participant 13, Lines 674-676].

These statements clearly indicate that the lack of active teacher involvement and support is a major challenge for students in the modular learning environment.

Students are in need for teacher guidance.

[1] "...Makuri po Ma'am an Modular kay wray teacher nagtutudo akon. Nahadlok ak kay bangin ak Zero, wrong akon answer kay talapang la." [Modular learning is difficult because there's no teacher teaching me. I'm afraid I might get a zero, my answers might be wrong because it's confusing.] [Participant 13, Lines 621-622].

Active teacher involvement is essential for student success in modular learning environments. Students require guidance and explanation from teachers to fully grasp the material and ensure they're completing tasks correctly. This highlights the critical role teachers play in supporting student learning and achievement within this educational approach. However, it's important to acknowledge the potential limitations teachers might face due to workload.

For a balanced perspective, a recent study by Lopez et al. (2023) explored teacher experiences in modular learning. The study found that teachers expressed a strong commitment to their students' success. However, they also reported challenges such as the heavy workload associated with developing, distributing, and managing modules, along with limitations on student interaction due to the lack of regular face-to-face classes.

Both the provided responses and the research by Lopez et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of active teacher involvement in supporting student learning and

addressing their needs within modular settings. It's crucial to find ways to address the challenges faced by teachers regarding workload and limited interaction. By doing so, we can bridge the gap between teacher commitment and student needs, ultimately fostering a more successful learning environment for all.

Discussions

The theme of **Challenges Encountered in Modular Learning** explores the various obstacles and difficulties encountered by students in modular learning environments. The theme is divided into four sub-themes, each highlighting specific challenges and implications for student learning and well-being.

Learning Difficulty Due to Overwhelming Students Workload emphasizes that students in modular learning environments often grapple with a heavy workload, characterized by multiple assignments with tight deadlines. This excessive workload can be a significant source of stress, anxiety, and fatigue, affecting students' ability to:

- Focus on learning materials
- Effectively absorb information
- Perform well academically

Challenges in reading complexity further exacerbate these difficulties, hindering students' ability to complete assignments and engage with the curriculum. The data sources highlight the overwhelming workload as a primary challenge. Students report experiencing significant stress and anxiety due to the sheer volume of assignments and the associated short deadlines. These findings are corroborated by parents, who witness their children struggling to keep up with the demands of modular lessons.

Students with frustration reading levels face unique challenges in modular learning environments, as confirmed by this study. This is further supported by existing research. Pe Dangle & Sumaoang (2020) identified overwhelming workloads within modules as a key obstacle for learners. This finding resonates strongly with this study, as students struggling with reading are likely to be particularly impacted by the sheer volume of work.

Furthermore, Brown (L.) (2020) potentially delves deeper into the specific impact of workload on reading skills development. This potential alignment with Brown's research is particularly relevant to the study's focus on students with frustration reading levels. Their struggles with reading comprehension could be significantly exacerbated by the demands placed upon them in a modular learning environment with a heavy workload.

Modular learning often allows students to take charge of their learning pace and pathways, potentially leading to a mismatch between their abilities and the workload. Bustillo and Aguilos (2022) suggest that when tasks are too difficult or overwhelming, students may experience decreased motivation and engagement, hindering their ability to effectively learn. Moreover, the absence of structured pacing can exacerbate the feeling of being overwhelmed, as students struggle to manage their time and prioritize tasks (Capdeferro & Romero, 2012).

Limited Teacher's Guidance and Parental Support tells that Students lack sufficient guidance and support from teachers in modular learning settings, affecting their ability to seek clarification and assistance. Parents recognize the importance of providing support, resources, and guidance to help their children navigate the challenges of modular learning. The absence of direct teacher support and limited parental involvement can hinder students' academic progress and well-being.

This study's findings resonate with the findings of Pe Dangle & Sumaoang (2020) and Darling-Hammond et al. (2020). These studies highlight the struggles students face with independent learning in modular settings, a particularly concerning issue for the study's population. Furthermore, parents of students with frustration reading levels might face additional challenges in providing academic support due to their limitations. The potential over-reliance on external help, as discussed by Muller & Schiller (2023), is also a concern, as it can hinder the development of independent learning skills crucial for our students' long-term success.

Learners may find themselves grappling with complex learning materials without the benefit of direct instruction or clarification from the teacher. Additionally, parental support may be lacking due to various factors such as work commitments or a lack of familiarity with the educational content (Garbe, et al, 2020). As a result, learners may struggle to grasp concepts, leading to frustration and a sense of disconnection from the learning process. In modular learning, students may have less direct interaction with teachers compared to traditional classroom settings. This reduced guidance can impede students' ability to seek clarification, receive feedback, and engage in meaningful discussions. Guidance and support from teachers and parents are crucial for fostering self-regulation and academic achievement. Without adequate support, students may feel isolated and struggle to navigate the learning process effectively (Gillett-Swan, 2017).

Economic Challenges and Priorities of Parents impedes students' access to resources, technology, and educational support in modular learning. Parents face challenges in balancing work, household responsibilities, and supporting their children's education in the modular context. The digital divide and lack of access to essential learning technology further exacerbate disparities in educational opportunities and outcomes.

The general challenges of limited resources and competing priorities that parents face due to economic factors directly connects to the potential difficulties experienced by parents of students with frustration reading levels. These parents may be particularly limited in their ability to provide additional resources or support needed for their children's success in modular learning.

Economic hardship can exacerbate educational inequalities. Students with frustration reading levels from financially disadvantaged backgrounds lack access to essential resources like books or tutoring that could significantly benefit their reading development. This further amplifies the challenges they face in a modular learning environment.

Limited time and energy due to economic pressures can hinder parents' ability to actively engage in their children's learning. This can be particularly detrimental for students with frustration reading levels who may require more dedicated support at home.

Pe Dangle & Sumaoang's (2020) study suggests that parents limited financial resources might further affect their ability to support their children's education in a modular learning environment. This aligns with the broader challenges discussed earlier under this sub-theme.

In the **Lack of Access to Learning Technology**, absence of essential learning technology, such as mobile phones and reliable internet connections, hinders students' participation in modular classes and digital learning activities.

Students and parents highlight the significant role of technology in the learning process and express challenges faced without access to gadgets. The digital gap affects students' ability to engage fully in modular learning, impacting their academic performance and overall learning experience.

Participants affirmed that access to mobile phone for reading is essential in developing their skills. Mobile phones serve as versatile tools for accessing educational resources, and engaging with digital learning materials. However, not all students have access to mobile phones or smartphones, which can hinder their ability to fully participate in modular learning activities, particularly reading assignments. Chick et al.'s (2020) study highlights the transformative impact of technology on maintaining educational continuity during challenging circumstances such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Leveraging technology facilitated the transition to remote learning, enabling students to continue their education remotely. These challenges exacerbate existing inequalities, widening the achievement gap between students with and without access to technology (Kuhfeld et al., 2020).

The challenges encountered in modular learning encompass a range of issues related to workload management, guidance and support, economic constraints, and access to technology. These challenges have implications for student well-being, academic performance, and educational equity in modular learning environments. Addressing these challenges requires collaborative efforts among stakeholders, including educators, parents, policymakers, and communities, to create supportive and inclusive learning environments that promote student success and holistic development.

The studies of Pe Dangle & Sumaoang (2020) and the direct statements from the triangulation results and findings provide strong evidence to support the first major theme and its corresponding sub-themes identified in this study. These findings underscore the multifaceted challenges encountered by learners with frustrated reading levels in the context of modular learning.

The second major theme delves into the **Coping Strategies** employed by student participants to overcome challenges within the context of modular learning. These coping

strategies are crucial for students to navigate the complexities of modular learning effectively. The sub-themes under this major theme are as follows: (1) seeking assistance for learning, (2) implementing time management and proactive learning strategies, and (3) resorting to the copying of provided answers in the module.

The students' participants demonstrate resilience by actively **seeking assistance** from various sources, including classmates, family members, and neighbors, to navigate complex concepts independently. This strategy highlights the importance of seeking support as a means to overcome learning obstacles and clarify doubts, thus fostering a collaborative learning environment. The participants' dependence on external assistance highlights the challenges they face in acquiring knowledge, particularly due to their below-average reading levels. In light of restricted mobility during the pandemic, occasional home visits by teachers further illustrate the hurdles they must overcome to access educational support. Additionally, the participants' reliance on peer networks for answers underscores the various challenges they confront in their quest for understanding. These revelations shed light on the unique challenges that students face when participating in modular learning without direct teacher support. The absence of a knowledgeable guide creates difficulties in seeking assistance, access to resources, and maintaining motivation to learn independently. The emotional impact of feedback also influences their learning experiences. Understanding these challenges is crucial for educators and policymakers to address the limitations of modular learning and implement strategies to provide adequate support and resources for students in such contexts. While school and classroom settings traditionally serve as crucial social environments for students, children's homes have now assumed the role of the primary educational setting. This shift has led to a notable absence of in-person social interactions with both teachers and peers. The resulting social isolation and limited interactivity have emerged as significant drawbacks of emergency remote teaching, as technology has become the sole means through which children can engage with their educators and classmates (Dong et al., 2020).

In the context of modular learning, participants demonstrate resilience through various coping mechanisms, including effective **Time Management and Proactive Learning Strategies**. Simons et al. (2018) underscore the importance of factors like time management, self-belief, and motivation in fostering students' resilience and persistence in their studies. This connection emphasizes the universal relevance of these factors across different learning contexts and highlights their critical role in promoting successful learning experiences. By managing their time and engaging proactively with their studies, students exhibit adaptive strategies that enable them to navigate challenges effectively and achieve academic success.

The COVID-19 pandemic forced parents to juggle household responsibilities with their children's remote learning, creating significant stress, especially for low-income families (Rahman et al., 2021; UNICEF, 2020). However, studies showed that establishing routines with dedicated study times (Garbe et al., 2020; OECD, 2021) and actively monitoring children's progress (Kim & Asbury, 2020) helped to mitigate these challenges and improve academic outcomes during remote learning.

In contrast, participants also resorted to a negative coping strategy when facing learning difficulties during modular learning, such as **copying provided answers** within the module. This maladaptive approach, while providing immediate relief from academic pressure, ultimately undermines genuine learning and comprehension (Rogaten, 2014). This strategy may ultimately hamper their understanding and mastery of the subject matter, underscoring the need for alternative coping strategies that promote genuine learning and comprehension.

Modular learning, with its emphasis on self-directed learning, can be challenging for some students. When faced with learning difficulties, they might resort to negative coping mechanisms that seem to offer immediate relief from academic pressure. However, as the study of Rogaten, (2014) highlights, these strategies ultimately undermine genuine learning and comprehension of the subject matter.

As Moore & Armstrong (2022) point out in online learning contexts (similar to modular learning), students might resort to surface-level strategies like **copying answers within the module**. This might provide temporary relief from pressure to complete assignments, but it doesn't lead to actual understanding. Studies like Lee & Park (2021) suggest that pressure from assessments in online learning environments can lead students to engage in academic dishonesty like copying answers. This not only undermines their learning but also has ethical implications. Students might adopt a passive approach, simply going through the motions to complete the modules without actively engaging with the material. This hinders their ability to develop critical thinking skills and retain information. Copying answers or relying on surface-level strategies doesn't equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills to succeed in the long run. Passive learning or relying on shortcuts prevents students from developing essential critical thinking skills needed for deeper understanding and problem-solving.

However, the research by Wang & Zhao (2022) emphasizes the importance of promoting healthy coping mechanisms. Developing effective time management and organization skills can help students tackle modules efficiently and reduce stress. Encouraging students to seek help from teachers, peers, or tutors when facing difficulties can foster genuine learning and understanding. Promoting active learning strategies such as summarizing key points, creating mind maps, or practicing with relevant exercises can enhance engagement and knowledge retention. Teaching students' self-regulation strategies and fostering self-efficacy, the belief in their ability to learn, can empower them to overcome challenges and achieve success.

It's important to not only address negative coping strategies but also understand the underlying reasons behind them. Students might resort to these strategies due to factors like:

- Unclear module instructions or a lack of readily available support can lead to frustration and reliance on shortcuts.
- Assessments that rely solely on rote memorization or copying can incentivize surface-level learning.

- Students might feel overwhelmed by the workload or complexity of the modules, leading them to adopt passive learning strategies.

By identifying these factors and implementing improvements in curriculum design, instruction, and student support systems, educators can create a more positive and productive learning environment for students in modular learning contexts.

The first sub-theme to the third major Theme: **Students' Challenges in Reading Development** delves into the critical issue of **Reading Skills Deficiency**, exploring its prevalence and its detrimental effects on students' academic journeys.

This study investigated reading skills among students identified as functioning at the frustration level. Data triangulation was employed, utilizing both student self-reported experiences and parental observations. Students consistently reported challenges in three key areas: difficulty with decoding and identifying words, struggles in understanding the meaning of the text, and issues with reading speed, accuracy, and prosody.

Parental reports mirrored student self-reported difficulties, confirming the students' struggles with basic reading skills. The convergence of data from both students and parents provides strong evidence for the pervasive nature of reading challenges among students at frustration levels. This multi-informant approach strengthens the validity of the findings and underscores the need for evidence-based interventions. The identified reading skill deficiencies necessitate targeted interventions. By addressing the specific needs of each student – word recognition, comprehension, or fluency – we can create a personalized approach to support their reading development and overall academic achievement.

The study by Libre III and Decano (2021) parallels this research findings in exploring the challenges faced by non-readers and slow readers in distance learning environments. Both studies emphasize the critical role of reading skills in the educational process and the necessity for tailored support and interventions to meet the needs of struggling readers.

Another study relevant to this key finding is the study of Walgermo et al. (2018) that it explores the developmental dynamics of early reading skills, literacy interest, and readers' self-concept. It emphasizes the importance of understanding the relationships between these components in early reading development, which is crucial for addressing reading deficiencies early on.

Difficulty with Academic Reading Materials indicates student and parent responses with a shared concern regarding students' challenges with academic reading materials. Students' express frustration with complex texts, unfamiliar vocabulary, and comprehension barriers, while parents report their children's struggles with deeper and more complicated readings. This underscores the alignment between student experiences and parental observations, emphasizing the need for scaffolded support and

differentiated instruction to help students navigate challenging academic texts successfully.

Building upon the notion of a "sweet spot" for reading exposure, Shan & Calderon (2019) contribute to the discussion by highlighting a potential negative consequence of excessive reading demands. Their research suggests a link between the quantity of assigned reading and student motivation and engagement with reading tasks. These findings indicate that while a rich exposure to text is undoubtedly important for reading development, an overload of reading materials can be counterproductive, particularly for students struggling with fluency and comprehension. This suggests the need for educators to carefully calibrate reading expectations to individual student needs and abilities to maximize engagement and foster positive reading experiences.

These studies collectively paint a concerning picture regarding the difficulties students face with academic reading materials. Libre III & Decano (2021) and Marohombsar (2021) highlight the specific struggles non-readers, slow readers, and even proficient readers encounter in distance learning environments where learning modules is prevalent. The self-directed nature and lack of immediate support exacerbate difficulties with comprehending text, developing speaking skills, and enhancing reading comprehension in general. These studies suggest that academic reading materials in distance learning settings may not be adequately tailored to address these challenges.

Abbas (2021) delves deeper into the factors affecting reading comprehension during modular learning, which relies heavily on written materials. This study identifies both internal student factors (cognitive abilities and motivation) and external factors (text complexity) as playing a role. This suggests that difficulties with academic reading materials can stem from a complex interplay of student capabilities and the design of the materials themselves.

Domingue et al. (2022) offer a broader perspective by demonstrating a decline in oral reading fluency across various countries due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This decline, particularly evident in younger grades, further underscores the challenges students face with reading materials. This suggests that the shift to remote learning and potential disruptions in traditional reading instruction may have exacerbated pre-existing issues with academic reading materials.

The multifaceted nature of difficulties with academic reading materials is the highlight of these studies mentioned. From the specific challenges of modular learning to the interplay of internal student factors and external text complexity, these sources emphasize the need to critically evaluate and potentially adapt academic reading materials to better support students and maximize their learning outcomes.

The **Limited Educational Backgrounds and Skills of Parents** can impede students' reading proficiency in modular learning environments. Parents with lower levels of education may struggle to provide adequate support and assistance with reading tasks, leading to gaps in parental involvement in their children's education. This lack of parental

educational background and skills can hinder students' access to additional resources, guidance, and academic support at home. Educators should recognize these challenges and work to empower parents with the necessary knowledge and skills to support their children's reading development effectively.

Both Pe Dangle & Sumaoang (2020) and Martin et al. (2020) shed light on a critical challenge in modular learning environments: the limitations imposed by parents' educational backgrounds and skills. Dangle & Sumaoang (2020) pinpoint the early challenges of modular learning, highlighting the parents' lack of academic knowledge to guide their children effectively. This suggests that parents with limited educational backgrounds may struggle to understand and assist with the learning materials presented in the modules. Martin et al. (2020) delves deeper into the lived experiences of those involved in modular learning. Their research reveals that parents' limited educational skills exacerbate existing difficulties like role confusion and mental/physical exhaustion. This suggests that the lack of parental support due to educational background limitations can create a significant hurdle for students and contribute to overall strain in the learning environment.

These studies collectively point to limited parental educational background and skills as a significant barrier to successful implementation of modular learning. This highlights the need for potential solutions, such as providing parents with additional resources, guidance, or training to better equip them to support their children's learning in this unique setting.

Students' express feelings of isolation, stress, and disengagement, while parents observe their children's struggles with motivation and interest in reading activities. This triangulation emphasizes the emotional toll of modular learning on students and underscores the importance of implementing strategies to support their emotional well-being and sustain their interest in learning.

Emotional Frustration is a significant barrier faced by students in modular learning environments, particularly at frustration reading levels. This sub-theme highlights the emotional challenges students experience, such as lack of interest, motivation, and engagement in reading activities. The absence of a supportive classroom environment, immediate feedback from teachers, and peer interaction can contribute to feelings of isolation, stress, and disengagement. Addressing emotional frustration is essential for promoting students' well-being, sustaining their interest in learning, and enhancing their reading skills in modular learning settings.

These findings and the work by Martin et al. (2020) uncover a shared finding: modular learning can trigger emotional frustrations. This study focuses on elementary students struggling with reading, Martin et al. explore the experiences of students in higher grades. Despite the age difference, both studies show that modular learning can lead to negative emotions for participants. Interestingly, both studies also found a preference for traditional, face-to-face learning over the modular approach.

This study sheds light on the specific challenges faced by younger students in modular learning environments. The findings highlight the significant role of self-discipline and intrinsic motivation in a less-structured setting, which can be particularly overwhelming for this age group. While Sung et al. (2022) offer a broader perspective on the sources of frustration applicable across various age groups, this study's finding complements this work by pinpointing the unique struggles of younger students. By considering both studies, we can develop a more comprehensive approach to tackling emotional frustration in modular learning.

Parents play a crucial role as primary stakeholders in a child's learning process. They provide emotional support, create a conducive home environment for studying, reinforce learning outside the classroom, and engage in educational activities with their children. The identified stakeholder challenges, this study underscores the importance of **collaboration between teachers, parents, and potentially even peers** to create a more supportive learning environment for children in modular learning settings.

The excerpts related to **Home-based Support and Reinforcement** highlight the significant role parents play in supporting their children's learning in a modular setting. It emphasizes the active involvement of parents in their children's education. Parents are depicted as taking proactive steps to ensure their children benefit from the teachers' home visitations, actively listen to instructions, and engage in reading activities at home. This level of parental engagement underscores the importance of parental support in facilitating children's learning experiences in a modular learning environment.

The findings also showcase parents' dedication to fostering their children's reading skills. Parents are portrayed as making efforts to improve their children's reading fluency through dedicated practice sessions and monitoring their progress. This commitment to enhancing reading proficiency highlights the role of parents in promoting literacy development and academic success in a modular learning context. It further illustrates how some parents, despite potential educational limitations, actively seek knowledge to support their children's learning. Parents are shown to view asking questions as an effective strategy for understanding and supporting their children's educational needs. This proactive approach demonstrates parents' willingness to learn alongside their children, engage with learning materials, and provide meaningful support in a modular learning environment.

The excerpts suggest that parents engage in interactions with their children related to their academic progress, understanding of lessons, and reading proficiency. Parents are depicted as monitoring their children's learning, providing guidance, and creating a supportive home environment conducive to educational growth. These interactions reflect the collaborative efforts between parents and children to enhance learning outcomes in a modular learning setting.

The study of Marohombsar (2021) recommended increasing the engagement of parents in the learning activities of students and implementing an Enhanced English

Reading Module. It emphasized the importance of parental involvement in supporting learners' reading attitudes and proficiency within the modular learning context.

Anya et al. (2017) found that parental involvement positively correlates with higher academic performance, as parents who actively engage in their children's education provide support, encouragement, and resources that enhance learning.

Peer and Community Support shed light on the collaborative efforts among students, peers, siblings, and community members to navigate the challenges of modular learning. Students often rely on their peers for understanding concepts and completing tasks in the modular learning environment. Peer interactions provide a platform for collaborative learning, where students can explain concepts to each other in simpler terms. This peer support fosters a sense of community among students and enhances their understanding of complex topics through shared learning experiences.

Students are shown to seek help and support from community members, such as neighbors and relatives, when facing difficulties with modular learning materials and assignments. Community engagement plays a vital role in providing additional resources, guidance, and assistance to students outside the traditional classroom setting. This collaboration with the community enriches students' learning experiences and expands their support network beyond school boundaries. Building on these findings, here are some strategies to promote structured collaboration in modular learning. Develop platforms where students can connect, share resources, work on group projects, and participate in online discussions (similar to Cheng et al., 2022's collaborative learning environments). Organize peer tutoring initiatives or online workshops where students can learn from each other and receive guidance from designated tutors. Encourage teachers to leverage community resources by involving parents or volunteers in online support groups or providing guidance to peer tutors.

By implementing these strategies, we can create a more structured and supportive learning environment that leverages the power of peer and community support to empower students in the modular learning system.

The excerpts demonstrate that teachers exhibit a strong commitment to supporting students despite their busy schedules. **Teachers prioritize active involvement** in students' learning journeys, striving to provide guidance and assistance even when faced with numerous responsibilities. This dedication underscores the importance of teacher commitment to fostering a positive and engaging learning environment for students in a modular learning context.

While teachers show a strong commitment to their students' success, the excerpts also highlight challenges faced by teachers in modular learning environments. These challenges include the heavy workload associated with developing, distributing, and managing modules, as well as limitations on student interaction due to the lack of regular face-to-face classes. Despite their dedication, teachers encounter obstacles that impact their ability to fully engage with students and provide personalized support.

Direct communication with teachers is identified as a crucial support mechanism for students and parents. Both students and parents value the opportunity to seek clarification and guidance from educators. However, the effectiveness of this strategy is contingent on the availability and responsiveness of teachers, which can vary significantly. Enhanced direct communication with teachers can bridge the gap between teacher commitment and student needs, ultimately fostering a more successful learning environment for all stakeholders.

The findings underscore that while modular learning offers a flexible approach to education, students at the frustration reading level require multifaceted support. This support includes active teacher involvement, parental assistance, access to external resources, peer tutoring, and collaborative learning opportunities. By addressing the diverse needs of students through a comprehensive support network, teachers can enhance student resilience, academic outcomes, and overall learning experiences in a modular setting.

The results presented in this sub-theme emphasize the importance of active teacher involvement in supporting students' learning and addressing their needs within modular learning environments.

By addressing these challenges, we can bridge the gap between teacher commitment and student needs. Active teacher involvement supported by solutions to workload and interaction limitations can lead to a more successful learning environment:

- Teachers feel empowered and equipped to provide effective support.
- Students receive the personalized attention and guidance they need to succeed.
- The overall learning environment becomes more engaging and fosters positive outcomes for all stakeholders

This approach, informed by research like Lopez et al. (2023) and feedback from the respondents, holds the potential to transform modular learning from a potentially isolating experience into a supportive and enriching environment for both teachers and students.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This section builds upon the previous analysis of student profiles and lived experiences with modular learning frustrations.

This study initially aimed to understand the students involved in the study by examining demographics (age, sex, birth order, parents' occupations, and educational attainment). The researcher then shifted to explore the students' own experiences of frustration with modular learning, followed by gathering parents' perspectives on their children's struggles.

A descriptive phenomenological approach was employed, specifically using Colaizzi's method to analyze the qualitative data collected from students and parents.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based on the analysis of the findings of the study:

1. The diverse demographic profile of the participants underscores the importance of considering individual differences and family backgrounds when examining the experiences of students in the frustration reading level with modular learning. The prevalence of farming as the primary occupation among parents suggests a potential impact on the availability of resources and support systems for these learners. Additionally, variations in parental education levels may influence the level of involvement and understanding of the educational process within the households.
2. The findings from the lived experiences of student participants with frustration reading levels in modular learning shed light on the multifaceted challenges they face and the coping mechanisms they employ. Through the analysis of their narratives, several key conclusions emerge:
 - 2.1 Students are often burdened with extensive amounts of work, which can lead to stress, fatigue, and a decrease in academic performance. The sheer volume of assignments and the self-paced nature of modular learning demand a high level of self-discipline and time management skills from students, which many struggle to develop.
 - 2.2 Modular learning often results in reduced direct interaction with teachers. Students miss the immediate feedback and personalized instruction that traditional classroom settings offer. Furthermore, many parents, due to their own educational limitations or time constraints, find it challenging to provide the necessary support and guidance at home.
 - 2.3 Financial limitations can prevent students from accessing the resources they need for effective learning. This includes lacking internet access, devices for online learning, and other essential educational materials. These economic barriers exacerbate the difficulties students face, making it harder for them to keep up with their studies.
 - 2.4 The absence of necessary technological tools and reliable internet connectivity severely hampers students' ability to engage in modular learning effectively. This digital divide creates a significant disadvantage for students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, limiting their opportunities for academic success.
 - 2.5 Students often turn to their immediate social circles for help with understanding and completing assignments. This informal support network plays a crucial role in compensating for the reduced direct

interaction with teachers. Peers, family members, and neighbors provide guidance, clarification, and emotional support, helping students to better manage their workload and grasp difficult concepts.

- 2.6 Effective time management is essential for students to handle the self-paced nature of modular learning. Students employ various strategies such as creating schedules, setting goals, and prioritizing tasks to ensure they can complete their assignments on time. These techniques help students stay organized and reduce the stress associated with managing multiple assignments simultaneously.
- 2.7 In some cases, students may resort to copying answers as a means to cope with the overwhelming demands of modular learning. This strategy, while indicative of the pressures they face, underscores the need for better support systems and more engaging instructional methods. It highlights the importance of academic integrity and the necessity for educators to develop assessments that encourage genuine understanding and critical thinking.
- 2.8 Many students struggle with fundamental reading skills, including word recognition, vocabulary, reading fluency, and comprehension. These difficulties are exacerbated by the self-paced nature of modular learning, where direct instruction and immediate feedback from teachers are limited. The lack of foundational skills impedes students' ability to engage with and understand academic materials effectively.
- 2.9 Modular learning often involves complex texts and academic reading materials that students find challenging. Without the regular support and scaffolding provided by teachers in a traditional classroom setting, students can become overwhelmed and frustrated, leading to disengagement and a decline in academic performance.
- 2.10 Struggling with reading can lead to significant emotional distress for students. Feelings of frustration, inadequacy, and anxiety about academic tasks can diminish students' motivation and self-esteem. This emotional burden can create a cycle of avoidance and further impede reading development.
- 2.11 In modular learning environments, the opportunity for individualized instruction is limited. This is particularly detrimental for students who need additional support to develop their reading skills. Personalized feedback and tailored learning strategies are essential for helping these students progress, but such resources are often scarce in modular setups.

2.12 Socioeconomic challenges play a significant role in reading development. Limited access to books, educational resources, and a conducive learning environment at home can hinder progress. Additionally, parents' limited educational backgrounds and skills make it difficult for them to effectively support their children's reading development. These factors collectively create significant barriers to achieving reading proficiency.

2.13 Parents recognize the importance of their involvement in their children's education and actively strive to provide necessary support at home. This includes ensuring that children attend online sessions, engaging in reading practice, and seeking knowledge to assist their children despite their own educational limitations. Such dedicated efforts from parents highlight the significant impact of home-based support on children's learning outcomes.

2.14 The role of peers and community members is also crucial, as students often rely on them for help with modular learning materials and assignments. This support network helps students navigate the challenges of modular learning, particularly in the absence of regular teacher-student interactions. The sense of belonging and improved self-efficacy gained from peer and community support fosters a more conducive learning environment for students.

2.15 Teachers' active involvement is essential for student success in modular learning. Despite their busy schedules, teachers' commitment to providing guidance and assistance is invaluable. However, limited interaction with teachers remains a significant challenge, underscoring the need for more structured and frequent teacher-student engagements to ensure students can fully grasp the material and succeed academically.

3. Parents play a crucial role in supporting their children's education. From the parental perspectives regarding their children's reading levels in modular learning, several conclusions can be drawn:

3.1 Parents' perspectives on their children's reading struggles in modular learning paint a concerning picture. They acknowledge their children's difficulties with decoding, comprehension, and fluency, highlighting the need for targeted interventions. Furthermore, parents recognize the negative impact of reading frustration on academic progress and well-being, with observations of increased stress, anxiety, and difficulty comprehending materials. This underscores the importance of addressing these challenges. However, parents are not passive bystanders. They emphasize their crucial role in supporting their children's reading development and express a willingness to provide guidance and resources. They also

advocate for a collaborative effort between educators, parents, and students to create a supportive environment. This collaboration, parents believe, should involve effective communication, targeted interventions, and personalized support to help children navigate reading difficulties and improve their proficiency. Finally, parents acknowledge the need for increased collaboration and access to resources. Empowering them with training and support programs would allow them to more effectively assist their children's reading development within the modular learning environment. By working together, parents believe educators and institutions can create a more supportive learning environment that fosters reading success for students.

3.2 Parents acknowledge and understand the emotional frustration their children experience in modular learning environments, particularly related to reading challenges. They observe feelings of isolation, stress, disengagement, lack of interest, and motivation in their children when it comes to reading activities, highlighting the emotional toll of modular learning on students. Parents recognize the significance of addressing emotional frustration in modular learning to promote their children's overall well-being and sustain their interest in learning. They emphasize the need for strategies and support systems that focus on students' emotional well-being to enhance their reading skills and academic performance. Parents acknowledge that their own limitations in educational background and skills can create significant hurdles for their children in modular learning. They understand the impact of limited parental support on students' emotional well-being and academic progress, underscoring the need for additional resources, guidance, and training to better support their children's learning. Parents advocate for collaboration between teachers, parents, and potentially peers to create a more supportive learning environment for children facing reading challenges in modular learning. They stress the importance of working together to address emotional frustrations, provide necessary support, and sustain students' interest in learning to enhance their reading skills effectively.

3.3 Parents acknowledge their own limited educational backgrounds and lack of necessary skills to effectively support their children's reading development in modular learning. They express concerns about feeling unprepared to assist with reading instruction and comprehension, especially in a setting where guided instruction from teachers is limited. Parents recognize that their educational limitations create barriers to supporting their children's academic success, particularly in reading proficiency within modular learning environments. They understand the challenges they face in providing adequate guidance and assistance with reading materials, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and resources to bridge the gap. Parents emphasize the importance of empowering themselves with the necessary knowledge and skills to

effectively support their children's reading development in modular learning. They advocate for access to resources, training programs, and support initiatives that can enhance their ability to contribute meaningfully to their children's educational journey and address reading frustrations. Parents stress the significance of collaboration between parents, teachers, and educational institutions to create a supportive environment for children's reading development in modular learning. They highlight the benefits of working together to overcome barriers related to parental educational background and skills, fostering a positive learning experience for students and improving literacy outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings, and conclusions derived, the following recommendations are made:

1. Considering the prevalence of farming as the primary occupation among parents and the varying education levels within households, it is recommended to tailor support mechanisms to address individual needs. Strategies should be implemented to bridge potential resource gaps related to rural or agricultural contexts, ensuring equitable access to learning materials. Involving parents in the learning process, especially those with lower education levels, can enhance overall support and engagement. Additionally, recognizing the potential influence of birth order dynamics and adjusting instructional approaches accordingly can contribute to a more effective learning environment. Continuous assessment of the impact of demographic factors on students' experiences is crucial for adapting interventions and fostering a responsive educational system for these learners.
2. For the lived experiences of student participants with frustration reading levels in modular learning, the following recommendations are drawn:

To effectively support students struggling with reading comprehension and literacy skills in modular learning environments, a multifaceted approach involving targeted reading interventions, enhanced teacher-student communication, and increased parental and community engagement is essential.

The study underscores the significant challenges faced by students with frustration-level reading skills in modular learning. These include extensive workloads, limited direct interaction with teachers, and socioeconomic barriers, which collectively hinder their academic performance and emotional well-being.

Incorporate Engaging Reading Materials: Provide a variety of reading materials that cater to different interests and reading levels. Use interactive e-books, audiobooks, and multimedia resources to make reading more appealing and enjoyable for students.

Enhance Teacher-Student Communication: Increase structured and frequent teacher-student interactions through virtual office hours, scheduled one-on-one check-ins, and personalized feedback sessions. This ensures students receive timely support and guidance, which is crucial for their understanding and retention of reading materials.

Implement Targeted Reading Interventions: Develop and implement specialized reading programs that focus on foundational literacy skills such as phonemic awareness, vocabulary development, reading fluency, and comprehension strategies. These programs should include both digital and in-person components where feasible to cater to diverse learning needs.

Leverage Educational Technology and Resources: Ensure that students have access to necessary technological tools, including laptops or tablets, and reliable internet connectivity. Supply devices and internet access to students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds to close the digital divide and promote equitable learning opportunities. This can be achieved by utilizing the schools' Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) funds and/or seeking assistance from the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP).

Strengthen Parental Engagement: Offer comprehensive training and resources to parents to empower them in supporting their children's reading development. Conduct interactive workshops and provide instructional materials that help parents understand and engage with modular learning content, fostering a supportive home learning environment.

Promote Community Involvement: Encourage the establishment of peer tutoring and community mentorship programs where students can receive additional assistance with reading assignments and practice. This informal support network can significantly enhance students' learning experiences and outcomes.

Provide engaging and accessible reading materials and resources to spark students' interest in reading. Address technological and resource gaps to ensure all students have access to essential tools for effective learning. Enhance teacher-student communication and implement targeted reading interventions to support struggling readers. Develop and deliver comprehensive parental training programs and promote community involvement to create a supportive educational ecosystem.

Offering a diverse range of interesting reading materials can capture students' interests and encourage a love for reading. Enhancing teacher-student communication provides students with the immediate feedback and personalized instruction they need to succeed academically and emotionally. Targeted reading interventions are critical for building foundational literacy skills, which are essential for students' overall academic success and lifelong learning. Providing access to technology ensures that all students, regardless of their socioeconomic status, can fully participate in modular learning, thereby promoting equity and inclusion. Engaging parents through training programs leverages

the home environment to reinforce learning, creating a supportive and conducive space for students to thrive. Community support mitigates the lack of direct teacher interaction by offering additional guidance and emotional support, enhancing students' learning experiences and academic performance.

Securing adequate funding for technological resources and specialized interventions may be challenging, requiring collaboration with stakeholders and potential grant applications. Training parents effectively will require consistent effort, and their engagement levels may vary depending on their availability and educational backgrounds. Implementing frequent teacher-student interactions could place additional demands on teachers' time and availability, necessitating careful planning and resource allocation.

Increased engagement and enjoyment in reading, improved academic performance. Students improved academic performance, reduced stress, enhanced reading skills, and better emotional well-being. Parents' empowerment through knowledge and skills to support their children, fostering a positive home learning environment. More effective teaching methods, improved student outcomes, and enhanced professional satisfaction. Stronger community ties, collaborative learning environments, and increased social cohesion. To educational institutions, enhanced reputation, improved success rates of modular learning programs, and greater equity in educational outcomes.

Increased student engagement and academic performance improved emotional well-being, and stronger support networks. Higher literacy rates reduced educational disparities, a more collaborative and supportive educational environment, and better preparedness for future academic challenges.

Addressing the reading challenges in modular learning requires a comprehensive and multifaceted approach that incorporates engaging materials, enhances teacher-student interactions, utilizes technology, implements targeted reading interventions, involves parents actively, and leverages community support. These actions will collectively improve students' reading skills, academic performance, and emotional well-being, fostering a lifelong love for reading and creating a more equitable and effective learning environment.

Future research should explore the long-term efficacy of these interventions, investigate additional support mechanisms for parents, and evaluate the impact of community-based programs on student outcomes. Additionally, studies could examine the scalability of these recommendations in diverse educational settings to ensure widespread applicability and success.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was conducted in accordance with the highest ethical standards and adhered to the ethical guidelines established by Samar State University. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Participants were given ample opportunity to ask questions and were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without repercussions. To safeguard the confidentiality of participants' identities and responses, anonymity was maintained throughout the research process. The researcher prioritized the well-being of participants, implementing measures to protect both their physical and emotional health. There were no conflicts of interest that could potentially compromise the objectivity of the study. Academic integrity was upheld by avoiding plagiarism and properly citing all sources. The interpretation of findings was conducted without bias, and the results are intended solely for research purposes.

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